

Program Report. Visiting Foreign Research Fellows

No. 30

*Defining Social Responsibility
Of The University*

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October 31, 2013

***Center for Research on International Cooperation
in Educational Development***

University of Tsukuba

CRICED

University of Tsukuba

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2013

International Fellow Research Visit

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Acknowledgments

This study would not have been possible without the support from Tsukuba University and specifically of professor Mariko Sato at CRICED who believed it was a topic worth exploring; I want to express my most sincere gratitude to the Directors of SEAMEO RIHED Dr. Sauwakon Ratanawijitrasin and Dr. Vipat Kuruchittham, for they believed I could represent SEAMEO RIHED in this endeavor; and I would also like thank my family and friends that always encourage me their warmth affection and support.

Abstract

The study analyzes social responsibility of the university to provide a comprehensive description of the phenomenon. In the search of common points that help us understand what falls within the concept and what does not, this research consisted of an extensive review of literature including previous research as well as documents serving as examples of universities acting responsibly and of organizations that promote universities' social commitment within and beyond the academic realm. The study depicts and integrates elements that characterize the concept of social responsibility at the university level and then reflects on ways and meanings of being responsible in the four areas where universities interact with society: teaching, researching, extension and outreach, and management.

By analyzing the roles the universities take through their institutional lives the study demonstrates that acting in a socially responsible manner constitutes a *way of being*. Social responsibility of the university speaks of who the universities are, who they want to be and how they put their missions and visions into action, how they serve and interact with the communities where they function and exist.

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1. Introduction

“[Social Responsibility of the University] *is a liberating and subversive function allowing society to discriminate whether the present order, authority and dominance institutions are useful concerning fundamental human needs and rights*”. (Navarrete Sepúlveda, Rojas, & Alvia Pantoja, 2012 citing Chomsky 2002)

1.1. Problem statement: the evolving university

Through history universities have evolved and changed; their roles and interactions with society have been attached to the signs of time, although tasks and commitments have remained somewhat the same as their primary responsibilities, those roles have evolved and given place to new engagements and expectations.

Universities have been conceived and understood as *clusters of knowledge* where research is done to constantly increase the body of theoretical knowledge and in a way to answer to practical problems in all realms of life, while through their teaching activities they have traditionally disseminated knowledge and offered professional training for qualified jobs.

In the past, they were restricted to a close circle of professors and students from wealthier families and they lived as isolated institutions, which led to the image of universities as *ivory towers*. Centers of knowledge that were only open to a few influential people and that would produce intellectual elites to serve in the higher ranks of the public administration; while in general research was conceived as a privilege activity only accessible to some professors.

Older universities set the basis for the progress of mankind, however they were narrow in access and too focused in their own inner world, they were generally isolated from the rest of society, except for the formal financial contributions of the governments and the production of professionals for the administration of the state. This meant that although they had the potential to contribute to the betterment of social life, they did not see themselves as agents of change. They were not normally understood as organically related to society, instead they held a kind of parasitic relation with the rest of society, this was typically the case of most universities during the years of the late middle ages and well into the 18th century.

The industrial revolution, the increasing urbanization and the advancement of democratization produced major changes to the roles traditionally assigned to the university. The new context brought about new demands onto the universities, for instance in the kind of education they were imparting, the content of their curricula and the kind of research that then started to shift from humanistic and philosophic to more practical and increasingly related to the need of producing scientific knowledge as featured by the liberal and positivist conception of knowledge that spread during the years of The Enlightenment.

Before this context universities changed how they used to portray themselves, the roles they were able and willing to take and the ways they used to interact with their environments and communities. Although higher education continued to be imparted in what Cunliff & Barthell (2011) describe as *a relic of the medieval universitas* there was a clear change as now students were expected to pay a fee to obtain skills that should be beneficial to enter the employment market that increasingly exceeded the public areas. However educational systems continue to promote the intellectual authority of the teachers, rendering them the imparters of the knowledge and the central player of the learning and researching processes.

Universities gradually became more active participants in the advancement of more efficient forms of social and economic development; they started positioning themselves in more

strategic locations within the social tissue as they realize their potential to connect the production of new knowledge and its dissemination in the form of skills and competences required by the new demands of the economic systems. This change in the traditional role of the university greatly affected the creation and the dynamics of economic and social developments of their communities and the ways they related to each other.

With the impacts on education of the industrial revolution changes happening at the social realm brought about transformations in the ways universities used to do things and interact with society. These changes in turn promoted more social changes in a kind of *virtuous circle* that boosted each other. Labarile (2009) noticed that in the beginning of the 20th century these changes could be observed in all types of universities, however it was more evident among those traditional institutions as the philosophical grounds upon which they had based the education they offered had to move from an elitist concept of education to a more mass oriented approach to allow access to more people.

A shift in the traditional values of the university could be seen towards more liberal ideals and more practical and vocational motivations in the development of curricula and programs; while another important change that started to take place then was the fact that research started to move from totally detached basic research to goal driven and industry-related research; at the same time fiscal and social accountability also started to gain space in the management of the institutions. Labarile (2009)

Post industrialism brought about a new scenario, a new paradigm that, once again, affected the way universities work and how they relate to their environments. With the increasing *massification* of higher education passing through formal institutions appears in most countries as an instrumental way to becoming informed citizens able to produce beneficial outcomes for society and in most cases a necessary bridge for vertical social mobility.

Among the changes observed in how universities evolved is the ways they carry out their traditional roles, as they use renewed approaches to more active learning, reducing the centrality of the teachers and progressively putting the students in a new and more central position; which has become increasingly evident in that modern universities encourage students to leave the traditional role of passive learners that only sit and receive knowledge and theory to become the protagonists of their own learning experiences. This new paradigm of learning has also sought to engage students to participate in the resolution of real problems, where they apply some of the knowledge they learn including skills related to analysis, synthesis, and evaluation of concrete activities to real life situations.

In this sense, Fields (2011) explored the idea that universities have shifted from *learning by memorizing to learning by critically understanding*; this is a clear change towards more student-centered approaches to education. According to this author universities have increasingly considered and developed new types of syllabi that include the notion of competency-based curricula, which makes students more confident at demonstrating the applicability of specific skills when they graduate as opposed to traditional students that were full of theoretical knowledge that many times had no connection to real life. This kind of argument challenges the traditional perspective of the universities as centers for *transmission*, as more student-centered activities bring better outcomes when taking place “outside of the university”.

Over time this kind of interaction of university with the community came to be known as *the third mission*, a blurry concept that refers to activities universities typically carry out *outside* their academic function and through which they promote positive social changes. This new

role compels them to think of systematic ways to contribute and develop programs that meet the demands from the surrounding environments in multiple ways.

McDonald (2006) describes this change as *community engagement*, where universities work cooperatively with and through different organizations and groups of people outside the university that are related by geographic proximity, similar interests or concerns to address issues affecting the well-being of their communities.

At the same time there has also been a change in the way people outside universities perceive them; the idea of the faraway ivory tower has been challenged as more consensus has grown among different actors on the idea that universities have important potentials to contribute to the general social betterment and hence a have a moral obligation to contribute to social development because they can be part of the solutions to the problems communities face.

The relation between society and higher education has become increasingly *organic* and so universities can no longer remain bubble-like clusters, they can no longer be the encapsulated entities they used to be in the past.

History shows that universities started creating and developing partnerships with different social actors at the community level seeking to generate new models of interaction where they could go beyond their typical roles and forms of extension and outreach, and sought to have communities participating in their programs not as outsiders or as research objects but also as partners in committing and combining ideas, resources and talents in order to find solutions to some of the issues communities face on daily bases. (Garber & Epps, 2010)

As universities engaged with their communities they did it through different engagements at local, national, and more recently at regional and global levels, depending on the scope of the activities they plan and implement and the partner with whom they collaborate. For the most part the local level has been the paramount of these engagements as they portray the more *intimate* linkages universities can have, where partnerships include both inter-institutional but most importantly inter-personal relations upon which the partnerships develop.

Globalization has contributed to reshape these roles, its interaction with society and the perceptions and expectations people have of the universities. Technological advancements increasingly interconnect all aspects of life and universities are not exception to this.

In a world of quick changes universities too adjust to better contribute in addressing some of the challenges societies face and develop strategies to respond to new demands. They too evolve to prepare their students and staff to be ready to think global and locally, with independent and critical thoughts yet functional to their societies, with ethoses that account with human values and that are sensitive to the needs of those with fewer opportunities.

The world faces challenging transformations that call for new responses. Within this context always developing technologies are confronting the universities to the reality of a much more complex and interconnected world far beyond their campuses, their cities or even countries. Universities are increasingly being called to attend problems of global scope.

Globalization and the development of more effective communications call for increasing democratization at all levels; these changes have progressively challenged the traditional idea of teacher-centered education, shifting towards approaches that are more student-centered and open to society, where learners expectations become more important and where their personal and direct experience are considered assets.

This context is making more evident the fact that students learn more, faster and better when they are interested in the process and when the practical aspects are related to real life events where they are a part of something actually making a contribution to the solution of

problems. Cunliff & Barthell (2011) explain this by saying that “*at its heart is the idea that students should be actively involved in their learning, an idea that most educators and citizens would support; at its extreme is the student as customer model.*”

This notion challenges the traditional ownership of knowledge by the professors and selected academics, shifting toward a new context where knowledge production and transmission happens on a more flexible and personalized fashion. Even the production of new knowledge and research as a whole have become more open and democratic, nowadays practically anyone can carry out research and have his or her findings published.

According to these authors it is within this contexts that considering social responsibility of the university as a strategy for knowledge production and transition has been getting stronger holds among most universities of the world; which in turn helps explaining the growing number of programs that request students to participate in internships or that provide academic framework and support for voluntary activities that seek to create benefits for the communities in general rather than for the academic community in particular.

As shown through the previous pages life of the university has historically happened around activities related to teaching, research and more recently to extension and outreach. These three elements constitute the *hard-core* activities all universities carry out. A few decades ago we have seen the appearance of a fourth element: *management*, as one more central element that, even if it has always been present, only recently has it become more evident, and hence challenging the traditional *trinity*.

That universities change and adapt over time is out of the question; however what is being put at stake now is rather in what direction and through what means should those changes happen, how can universities be better prepared to respond to the needs of their societies and how can their potentials to generate positive social changes be boosted.

These questions touch upon the issue of *engineering the university* as an organization that should account with well-grounded strategic plans based on the needs of those they aim to serve and by providing a kind of education that is both of good quality and that contributes to the betterment of life as a whole. In other words conceiving a revised manner in which universities interact with their environments and communities.

1.2. What the research is about: key questions

The pages above demonstrate that even if the university has evolved over history some aspects have remained constant, which represent and define the roles that are assigned to the university and how it relates to the rest of society. Creating new knowledge (research), disseminating it (teaching) and contributing to the betterment of their communities (extension and outreach) have been determining functions of the university, however how can we know if they have they been carried out responsibly? If the answer is yes, what does that mean? And if the answer is no; why not?

The way universities interact with societies where they exist determine the kind of research they do and the forms of teaching they use; however the issue of university commitment to social problems remains somewhat less clear and this is what the study aims to address. Why do universities commit with their local communities in trying to find solutions to some of their problems? How do they do it? How does engagement affect the roles of the university? And, how do these commitments reflect who the universities are and wish to be?

1.3. Justification

The ideas presented in previous paragraphs reflect the need to consider universities in relation to their environments and surroundings. Higher education institutions have a special kind of responsibility toward society because they are the place where future leaders and workers are formed and where future professionals get their first views of the world.

It is imperative for universities to constantly reflect on and remember that they provide much of the formation to the future leaders and those making decisions that affect society as a whole, they have a key role in determining the direction toward which society heads for. This pushes universities to go out of their comfort zones and start seeing themselves beyond the bubbles in which they have traditionally functioned.

Universities have been perceived as spaces where ideas are cultivated and nurtured, as such they represent spaces of rationality, growth and peace -which is in itself a positive thing- that, however becomes meaningless if they are unable to *spill* those benefits to society as a whole.

Peralta Portillo (2011) describes this in the graphic idea of world becoming a *global Titanic*, as a luxurious ship full of techno-scientific developments that moves however without a precise direction, putting its own survival at stake. He argues that most leaders governing countries, centers of power and leading public and private institutions (as the directors of this Titanic) are university graduates applying skills and knowledge on daily bases as they use the sciences, technologies and skills they learnt during the years of their academic formation. And yet they are also the cause of many of the problems societies face as the result of reproducing ideas learnt during the time they spent in their universities.

A clear feature of today's formation in the universities is the increasing fragmentation and growing gap between hyper-specialized knowledge and the common citizen, this tendency has brought about new barriers to the interaction of the university with their communities, and may be generating more of the chronic blind eye attitude among academics toward the effects universities produce to the world as a whole, and also by failing to systematically address most of today's social and ecological crisis.

The 21st century represents a crucial turning point where not only reforms are needed but most importantly when universities are being called to make a serious reflection on the meaning of what they produce in terms of new knowledge, formation of leaders and how they interact with the rest of the social tissue.

A number of paramount developments have taken place since the early 1990's that touch up on the issue of the social role of the university as a central player in the development of a better world and fairer societies. These initiatives put a high number of expectations upon the universities, and in a way they take it for granted that universities are willing and ready to take the challenges set there. So in order to give more support to those initiatives this research aims at portraying and defining what social responsibility of the university is so as to provide more solid ground to those initiatives to materialize and to bring more and better answers. The most prominent examples of these initiatives are:

1. The *Talloires Declaration* (1990) where representatives from universities from around the world agreed on the need to gather their expertise and resources for the establishment and implementation of community programs that benefit both education itself and social development. The goal set therein is to strengthen the civic role and social responsibility of universities that commit to become leaders in developing, creating, supporting and maintaining sustainability. (Favish, Mcmillan, & Ngcelwane, 2012)

Initially concerned about environmental pollution, the depletion of natural resources and the impact of inequitable and unsustainable production and consumerism as sources of poverty

and social exclusion, these university leaders put forward the fact that higher education has a major role in the education, research, policy formation, and information exchange necessary to make necessary changes and contribute to the solution of some of these problems hence fostering the social role of the university.

2. The call for active engagement of the universities born out of the Kellogg Commission (1999) that resulted in a group of high profile academics that criticized the attitudes of universities (teachers and managers) as they had traditionally maintained a *comfortable gap* between the university and the rest of the communities. The commission set a network to systematically research and promote the commitment of higher education institutions toward social betterment. In its first report the Commission described the attitude of those scholars that had kept higher education as an impermeable cluster in the following words:

“To the non-academic, the university is a near-inscrutable entity governed by its own mysterious sense of itself [. . .] we [academics] are so inflexibly driven by disciplinary needs and concepts of excellence grounded in peer-reviews, that we have lost sight of our institutional mission to address the contemporary multidisciplinary problems of the real world” (p. 20).

This was the starting point for series of initiatives leading to more systematic commitments from universities in the United States and the rest of the world toward practical and concrete contributions to a number of social problems.

3. *The UN Declaration of the Millennium*, that in 2000 set the Millennium Development Goals, seeking to: 1) eradicate extreme poverty and hunger; 2) achieve universal primary education; 3) promote gender equality; 4) reduce child mortality; 5) improve maternal health; 6) combat HIV/AIDS, malaria, and other diseases; 7) ensure environmental sustainability; and 8) develop a global partnership for development.

Although universities are not mentioned in the Goals of the Millennium or in the Declaration, it is clear that higher education institutions have a crucial role in the achievement of those goals; it is their research, teaching and extension and outreach work, their policy analysis among many other activities that provide societies with tools to achieve these goals. Through their work universities contribute and address universal problems and bring local solutions in many areas and forms, these relate for example to:

- Consolidate democracy and human rights as they carry studies on governance, leadership or security.
- Contribute to human dignity through work and research they do in many fields like in medicine, education, etc.
- Eradicate poverty by participating in programs about food security, or combating poverty, social exclusion and other forms of social vulnerability.
- Seek to balance sustainable development, competitive industries and economies with environmental protection through the work and research they do in agriculture, biology, energy or environment.
- Promote peace and security by participating in projects on legal aid or studies on the construction of peace.

4. *The ISO 26000* reference on social responsibility (2010) represent yet another effort from the International Organization for Standardization in an attempt to provide advice for organizations wishing to act as socially responsible agents of change.

Different from other ISO standards this one is not certifiable and it works as guidelines suggesting what socially responsible behaviors and programs should be like. Although the value of ISO 26000 is limited in terms of certifying standard management, it offers a common

ground to understand what social responsibility means and how it can be applied by any organization. Acceptance and adjustment to the standards by any organization is a voluntary matter, but the document itself serves as a catalyst and encourages institutions to consider their roles and interactions within the broader social context.

The standard defines social responsibility as the *will of some organizations to incorporate social and environmental considerations to their decision making process and to become accountable for the impacts that those decisions and activities bring*; which implies a behavior that is ethical and transparent, that contributes to sustainable development, respects the legal systems and that is coherent with international standards. This also implies that social responsibility must apply to the organization as a whole and not only to some parts of it; that it materializes in everyday interpersonal and inter-institutional relations, and that considers the interests of all parts involved.

Wentzel (1991) argues that although ISO 26000 have been originally thought for the business sector, because they are applicable to all social organizations, they too can apply to the management of the university. According to this author in the educational sector, different from seeking to generate economic profits, universities contribute to produce knowledge and to educate the public and raising its cultural level; as such universities too can make use of the norms there to systematize their initiatives into more socially responsible approaches.

The arguments presented in previous paragraphs justify this research both in theoretical and practical terms as understanding what social responsibility of the university means, where and how it works can facilitate the process of making universities aware of their potentials and social significance and eventually more responsible and socially sensible.

1.4. Relevance

As explained, universities are now more than ever before expected to come out from their comfort zones, to interact with the rest of society and to produce positive changes from that interaction. But how are they to do it? What channels can they use to achieve such broad goals without detracting who they are and what they are meant to do?

A likely answer to those questions is the implementation of more responsible behaviors at the university level however the diversity of ways in which universities conceive and implement their socially responsible behaviors and initiatives renders the higher education scenery very complex, particularly in terms of new goals and roles.

According to Gaete Quezada (2011) it is increasingly clear that identifying and implementing programs that correlate the university to their environments allows them to revise their policies and strategies, to find new directions to their teaching and researching activities, and in so doing to better define their mission and vision.

Understanding what social responsibility of the university means is the first step towards acting responsible and this is the primary goal of the research.

1.5. Goals and objectives

The study seeks to achieve general goals that relate to:

- Contribute to the understanding of the phenomenon of social responsibility of the university and what motivates socially responsible initiatives.
- Analyze the phenomenon to better understand its nature, dimensions and forms.
- Facilitate the implementation of new projects based on that understanding.

- Promote a deeper sense of responsibility among universities.

In order to achieve those goals the following objectives guide the research:

- Portray what motivates universities to act as socially responsible agents.
- Describe what social responsibility of the university is according to different theoretical approaches.
- Provide an overview of the areas where universities commit and the benefits that are normally expected.
- Explore connections between social responsibility and universities social interaction:
 - in their teaching, specifically through service learning;
 - in their production of knowledge through engaged research;
 - in extension and outreach through specific initiatives of this kind; and
 - in management in the ways they are administered and held accountable.

1.6. Methodology

Data collection

Data used for the study was obtained from a literature review focused on social responsibility as a general topic and then narrowed down to the specific area of the university in practical matters and experiences being implemented by universities.

The review included theoretical aspects of the phenomena as well as empirical research and anecdotic information available from previous research and from data provided by universities in their websites used as examples.

All data was collected through an extensive review of online available literature during the period January ~ June 2013.

Data analysis

Data from previous research was reduced and analyzed according to areas of analysis that help to describe the phenomenon. These areas are:

- Motivations behind the implementation of socially responsible initiatives
- Definition and features of the concept of social responsibility of the university
- Areas where social responsibility of the university is observed
- Kinds and roles of different stakeholders
- Expected benefits
- Service learning
- Engaged research
- Extension and outreach, and
- University management

Interpretation of results

Once key research papers and initiatives were identified, information there was reduced and classified into the sections mentioned above. Key aspects of those papers were extracted and combined into a comprehensive body of complementary and contrasting approaches to each particular area of analysis.

Research focus

The research is based on the premises of theories like the critical social theory and social constructivism as starting points from where socially responsible activities are designed and implemented as a model for academic formation and social change.

Because of this the research focuses on institutional motivations, regulations and procedures carried out by the universities aimed to act as responsible agents of social change and to improve quality of life of their communities by carrying out initiatives and projects that overflow the traditional academic work by focusing in the different forms in which universities interact with society. As such the study focuses on:

- Motivations at the university level to act responsibly and to implement social projects.
- Policy and mechanisms that seek to promote universities' roles as clusters that cultivate socially sensitive human resources and committed graduates.
- Ways in which social responsibility is included in the academic formation of the students to provide real life experiences to pedagogically support the learning process.
- Strategies to better integrate research and management as ways of social interaction.

Scope of the research

The research focuses on the four areas of interaction where the university relates with other social agents and communities outside the academic realm. As such it focuses on the work universities do in teaching, researching, extension and outreach and management and how activities carried out in these areas render the work of the university socially responsible.

1.7. Structure of the study

The study is structured as follows:

Chapter 2 presents the literature review covering issues like the roles the university over history and its contribution toward the notion of citizenship based on responsible civic relations. It also covers research available on service learning, engaged research, extension and outreach as well as some critical views of the social engagement of the university.

Chapter 3 presents the methodology utilized for the study providing details on its context, the questions guiding it, its goals and objectives, research focus as well as an explanation of how data was collected, analyzed and classified.

Chapter 4 draws *first kind of findings* from the review that help defining social responsibility of the university based on the motivations that make universities act as responsible agents by using the resources they account with in ways that render them accountable. The chapter analyses university interactions that materialize as partnerships with stakeholders typically outside the academic realm; it offers a brief description of the benefits that can be expected from universities that embark on the road of being socially responsible.

Chapter 5 looks at a *second type of findings*, specifically at how universities act as socially responsible agents when they interact with society through the four main roles it is meant to fulfill: 1. Teaching -through service learning-; 2. Responsible research -by engaging with external partners in engaged research-; 3) By setting measures that fall under the category of extension and outreach -that are aimed at bringing the university in closer contact with communities outside the academic realm-; and 4) University management -analyzing how universities are administered in the aim of acting responsibly-.

Lastly, chapter 6 presents the final observations on how for the universities, being responsible implies a form of identity as it depicts who the universities are and want to be.

2. Literature review

Social responsibility of the university appears in the academic literature as a new research topic even if the debate on the roles of the higher education has a long history. Attempts to approach it have emerged from developments in other areas where *social responsibility* has taken hold such as those of corporate social responsibility and community engagement.

As a research topic, social responsibility of the university presents a wide interacting universe of fields that deserve consideration to comprehend the nature of the phenomenon, the following pages present an overview of the perspectives from where social responsibility of the university has been addressed and it is supported by examples from previous research and universities' practice. The review covers the following areas:

1. *Role of the university* to provide an overview of *what* is expected from them in terms of activities beyond teaching and researching.
2. *University and the construction of citizenship* as they go hand in hand and boost each other.
3. *Normative perspective* as the base from where to construct socially responsible initiatives and how those efforts should be implemented in order to promote more effective outcomes.
4. *Service learning* as an expression of responsible initiatives that relate to pedagogical aspects, where universities engage in the solution of social problems.
5. *Engaged research* as scholars *overflow* traditional research to include *non-academic* stakeholders and processes in their research to identify social problems and solutions.
6. *Extension and outreach* that bridges the university with communities outside campus by implementing projects that create broad social benefits.
7. *Critical views of the social engagement of the university* argues that these initiatives may render universities weaker as engagement *diverts* the goals they are meant to address.

2.1. Role of the university

It is widely agreed that the role of the university has always been to serve and strengthen society at large through teaching and researching. They create social capital by preparing their students to be professionals involved in the life of their local, national and global societies; and *this* is especially where they have a social responsibility.

According to Bourner (n.d.) engagement of the university as a form of responsibility was born and evolved during the 20th century when education institutions were pushed to move from their peripheral position to more central ones as they took new roles resulting from changes in national economic and politic systems. Over time scientific research became relevant in the design of public policies and productive methods making universities more crucial for both the development of those activities and as the *producers of human resources*. These changes transformed universities as new activities progressively overflowed teaching and research.

According to this author the *service part* of the universities' missions became more relevant because governments gradually increased their expenditures to support universities, which in turn brought new expectations about the contributions universities were to do for the wider community. He provides an overview on the ways universities changed in mainly three stages classifying them into: 1. *Medieval university* -12th through 15th centuries, that served the Church, looking to enhance piety and developing scholasticism-; 2. The *early modern university* -16th through 19th centuries, that served the education of students, seeking to enhance national development based on humanistic values-. And 3. The *Humboldtian*

university -late 19th through late 20th centuries that advanced secular knowledge to develop critical thinking and science through empirism-.

In a related article Aviram (1992) argues that the roles of the universities have changed as a result of the changes in the configuration and the conceptions upon which they have been built, especially in terms of the functions and nature of the kind of research they do and the roles they take based on their own identity and those assigned by the society. He proposes a set of 3 types of universities depending on their goals, classifying them as entities seeking to become: 1. *Service stations* that provide guidance and assistance to society; 2. *Ivory towers of knowledge* as they propagate knowledge and research; or 3. *Culture frontier posts* working as workshops where national cultures are developed and protected.

A second classification he proposes relates to the role institutions give to research and the teaching models they use; here universities are grouped as: 1. Universities within the patrons of the traditional or medieval university; 2. Liberal or English universities -that focus in learning of liberal arts-; 3. Positivistic or French model universities -that focus on research as a detached and objective activity-; 4. The relativist or utilitarian universities -that brought the notion that knowledge and science had to be useful for society hence seeking to develop more practically oriented research-; and 5. Humanist or German universities -that existed shortly in the university of Berlin and that promoted a purely humanistic approach-.

The author argues that the forth model (relativist and utilitarian) prevails in today's societies where the traditional scientific method of the positivism has disintegrated to allow for more relative views on how the university should function (including the financial aspects of the management) and making it a more complex and permeable entity.

Cooper (n.d.) asserts that a new form of interaction and a new role of the university started to mushroom as a mission to contribute to socio-economic and cultural developments, when universities started to understand that they could carry out research inspired in real life and toward social change, overcoming traditional visions of the need to carry basic and objective research. According to this author during 19th and early 20th centuries a *first academic revolution* took place that connected the earlier first mission of the teaching to a second one of researching, which opened the way for new developments into a *second academic revolution* that brought together the first, second and newly born third roles of the university together; meaning that teaching and researching had to contribute to social development.

In a similar way Gie (2007) asserts that universities by virtue of their nature contribute to social improvement as they generate knowledge and promote intellectual development, which function as products of social interaction and engagement. If universities aim at being socially productive they need to do it by contributing to the sustainable improvement of their communities by means of empowering and uplifting the societies they are meant to serve.

Within the context of societies going through a process of democratization, the author argues that if universities want to maintain their social status and continue to provide good and assured standards of education, they need to incorporate *knowledge-based community service* into their teaching, learning and research practices in a systematic way.

In the context of universities in Latin America Ayuso & Sasia Santos (2008) analyzed how the use of terminology like *sustainable development* and *environmental awareness* have had a growing impact in the way universities and teachers think and structure contents and the ways they teach. Although this terminology may initially seem foreign to educational services, they have brought about new systems of ideas and pedagogical approaches that tend to include the matching of skills and resources from universities and communities as a synergic element for their mutual development and benefit.

From a different perspective Vallaey (2009) and authors like Madorrán-García (2012, citing Vallaey 2006) approach social responsibility of the university from the point of view of the management of the institutions and how the administration and control of the impacts universities generate make them into responsible and accountable entities.

As a last example of the ample discourse Shapiro (2005) proposes a scheme according to which the main role of the university has always been acting as source of critical ideas and innovation for social development -regardless of whether they are financed and work as public or private institutions-. In this author's views higher education has an inherent social role, which simply put means that universities cannot avoid having a critical role in raising questions that society does not want to ask and generate ideas that help invent the future.

2.2. The university and the construction of citizenship

A number of researchers analyzed experiences of universities taking up the challenge of implementing projects that link university and community, as a result a growing amount of literature shows interesting linkages in terms of how democratization processes in some countries are boosted by engaging the universities while at the same time promoting democratization within academic clusters themselves. Many of these research pieces help understand the nature of the phenomenon and serve as guidance for ongoing and future enterprises. Concrete instances of the implementation of university engagement and democratization are countless, however and only to provide a few examples the following paragraphs present a few illustrative cases.

Examples of this kind of literature can be found in pieces like Gie's (2007), which provides an extensive literature review that expands on an international perspective regarding the civic roles and social responsibilities of higher education, by focusing on the South African case of its National Government's White Paper on the Transformation of higher education which was used as a starting point for the implementation of service learning projects in the country coinciding with its democratization process.

Adamson-Fiskovica, Kristapsons, Tjunina & Ulnicane-Ozolina (2009) studied the *third mission of the university* in the democratization process in Latvia; they demonstrate that there is an emerging consensus in that after reopening of the country, universities took up missions that exceed their education and research goals. The end of the centralized period under the model of the USSR gave universities a new ground where they renew their contact with society as more than mere producers of knowledge and by becoming agents of social change that include issues like the development of linkages between universities and the private sector.

In a similar way in their book *Community Service and Social Responsibility in Youth* Youniss & Yates (1997) analyze community service as a beneficial set of activities that account with effects on the students' political and moral identity. By using a case study from an urban predominantly black high school in Washington DC, they argue that socially responsible commitments help molding positive attitudes both in learning and in the way teenagers identify themselves with their communities.

Another example is Culum's (2005) piece that analyzes universities in Croatia that carry out their *civic missions* by implementing policies to produce good citizens that engage with their communities (such as development needs, poverty reduction, health care access and quality, hunger, unequal access education, among many other issues); he shows that universities make important contributions by conducting research, by educating the students to be responsible citizens; and by providing forums for dialogue and cooperation.

In an attempt to systematize knowledge on the issue of social activity of the universities Crews (2002) provides a comprehensive sourcebook on learning services in higher education, the piece includes an extensive review of literature, online resources and access to discussion groups and forums that can greatly help in looking at what universities are currently doing.

As a whole, these pieces support the idea that contributions universities do to their communities go beyond the mere academic interests of areas of specialization and location.

2.3. Normative perspective

As social responsibility of the university consolidates and more institutions show interest and implementing their own initiatives more authors have taken up the effort of describing the issue and have gone beyond to a more *normative perspective* to set guiding lines or strategies for universities to act as socially responsible entities. Articles of this kind seek to involve universities as active *citizenship builders*.

Peralta Portillo (2011) for example, analyzes social responsibility by focusing on universities in Venezuela; he departs from the assumption that being socially responsible is a transversal and inherent aspect of the education universities impart. To support that idea he provides an explanation on the origin of responsibility based on the juridical concept derived from ancient Roman law where responsibility relates to harm caused to others and as a subjective duty to do what is at one's reach to help others based on ethical motivations. According to the author socially responsible initiatives help overcoming egocentrism and building a sense of altruism among students and graduates, hence these principles apply to individuals and institutions alike and in the case of universities this refers to the need to educate future professionals with a sense of responsibility and social commitment.

Gaete Quezada (2011 and 2010) analyzes the phenomenon by looking at the experiences of Spanish universities and argues that the issue has achieved increasing visibility in recent years in the areas of management and strategic planning while the same can be seen in the number of institutions providing subjects and courses on ethics with requirements that include socially responsible activities within the curricula of universities in the region.

According to his theory there are at least three areas where socially responsible initiatives take place: 1. The managerial level of the universities; 2. The normative areas where universities seek to achieve desirable goals; and 3. The voluntary activities organized within the universities. From this stand point the author analyzes different programs implemented in the Spanish context from where he suggests the above tripartite perspective serves as a guide toward the implementation of socially responsible activities.

In a similar fashion Ayuso & Sasia Santos (2008) develop the notion that social responsibility of university and its engagement with society is a valid strategy that allows them to create new educational models. These authors focus on the case of universities in Latin America and their role and duty to place themselves at the service of social justice. To help universities achieve this, these authors offer guidelines on the conditions required for the universities to account with the leadership skills they need so as to be recognized as responsible institutions and agents of change. They carry out a detailed analysis of how ethics should guide the decisions of the universities at the management and teaching levels in order to promote collective actions towards the improvement of social standards.

Demonstrating that the phenomenon has common features in all regions of the world, in a similar way Mehta (2011) examines the roles of the universities in the context of the Middle East and makes a call upon university managers for them to set goals at the time of involving institutions with activities outside academia. The author spots strategies universities use to

empower themselves and societies; and he explores the ways in which universities cooperate with society by establishing linkages of student bodies' with their communities.

On a more practical approach Labarile (2009) analyses the connections between universities and local communities in pursuit of the attainment of developments beyond the economical realm. She focuses on the ways higher education institutions collaborate with other social partners and how they work in order to agree on common strategies for economic growth and makes a deep description of how partnerships can be built including different actors like the state governments and the universities in order to jointly find solutions.

2.4. Service learning

If we assume that universities are institutions that *willy-nilly* and by their own nature are *socially productive* and contribute to advancement of society, then the question is how to bridge the contributions they can make with the potentials they have; how do they make their traditional roles (teaching and researching) more socially effective? In the case of teaching, the answer lies in what academics and practitioners call *Service Learning*.

This new educational paradigm consists on giving a pedagogical orientation and a systematic learning content to activities where students engage in projects designed from the university to bring practical answers to some of their community problems. Among the preeminent authors in this current of thought was Dewey, whose work *Experience & Education* (first published in 1938) opened the door to the quest about this new pedagogical paradigm.

He analyzed *progressive education* as a complement to traditional one and he defined it as bodies of knowledge that pass from a generation to the next as information and skills; he focused on *experimental learning* which brought a new educational philosophy, where he developed a *theory of experience* demonstrating that the *boredom* content of traditional education made the learning process slower and less effective, hence the need to re-think education in terms of how to make the learning process a continuity of experiences. Over time, in 1963, Dewey was of the opinion that interaction, reflection and experience could enhance the learning process. Dewey's formula: *Experience plus Reflection equals Learning*, had laid a foundation for experiential learning and has made a significant contribution to educational paradigms of the 20th and 21st centuries.

The model he proposed includes overcoming traditional insular environments of schools by giving students extra motivation to learn by focusing in three aspects: 1) giving them *freedom of intelligence* -free thinking, observing and judging- to allow ownership of the learning process in the students; 2) giving *meaning and purpose to learning* –where teachers provide orientation to the purposes of the learning by making observations, assessments and judgments a part of the students' life to help determine significance of lessons learnt-; and 3) giving the educator an important role in terms of *creating* educative experiences by developing learning materials and goals within the scope of ordinary life-experience.

The idea presented by the paradigm changed the role of the educator that now is invited to not only *impart information* but also to create a link between theory and practice in a contextualized-experience to allow for progression in a more effective learning process.

Following the path set by Dewey some authors further developed the idea that the learning process can be enhanced by engaging the students with real life experiences. Vallaeys, (2009) for example developed a theoretical framework that links social responsibility to a system of management of the impacts of universities in their four essential processes of management, academic training, knowledge production, and social participation.

He argues that far from being a mere repetition of usual social commitment discourse universities can take advantage of socially responsible activities to promote their academic innovation, institutional coherence, and social pertinence.

Dana Moore Gray (in Cunliff & Barthell, 2011) compiles a set of different definitions that describe service learning as activities focusing on serving a community through actions that are not for profit while reinforcing values of good citizenship; creating a *win-win situation* for students (as they apply their knowledge and skills in the real world) and serve people outside the academic realm (that receive extra assistance in whatever form). According to her this is what makes service learning a form of experiential education in which students engage in activities that address human and community needs together with structured opportunities designed to promote student learning and development.

Deepening the understanding of the phenomenon Furko & Billig (2001) present enriching views on the different meaning of *community service* as opposed to *service learning*. They differentiate those concepts in that the first involves a wider range of actors that carry out activities to provide solutions to problems of the community, while service learning has a pedagogical goal and content that focuses on the learning experiences of individuals while practically applying their knowledge in assisting different communities.

According to them *engaged activities* by students are academically oriented and have a goal of enriching the learning experience by exposing students to real life situations; while typical *community service* has a more elitist perspective attached to social obligations born from a moral superiority of those performing the service. These authors differentiate both *social service* from *learning service* in saying that the second includes aspects such as: clearly identified learning objectives; student involvement in selection or designating the service activity; and theoretical bases upon which the initiatives are constructed and developed.

In this sense Peric (2012) contributes to the better understanding of the differences between traditional education and the pedagogical concept of service learning in saying that on one hand *traditional education* focuses on theory, the memorization of other people's knowledge, where the learner is an observer with an unilateral learning process delineated by the teachers, in a system that provides predictable and homogenous learning outcomes based on an objectivist epistemology for any research. While on the other, *service learning* is presented as a method where students learn from theory and practice, through a personal process, where the students acquire previous knowledge and participate in the creation of new one. This model makes the distinction between teachers and students rather dialogical in the learning process, especially because issues being treated are unpredictable. Another important difference is the lack of a clear preview of the outcomes and the fact that ignorance in itself is considered as a potential resource for further creation of knowledge.

In a related article Wentzel (1991) describes benefits socially responsible universities generate and concludes that committing students to engaged activities offers valuable development outcomes and that these initiatives are instrumental in the acquisition of knowledge and the development of cognitive abilities. She argues that engaging students and researchers boost a sense of responsibility among students, parents, teachers and the community as a whole. She coincides with other authors in that socially responsible activities facilitate learning and improve outcomes by promoting positive interactions with teachers and peers and, from a motivational perspective, by giving students additional incentives and sense of ownership.

And a last contribution that was considered important for this review is Field's (2011) analysis on how the concept of competency-based curriculum is shifting the focus of the efforts in the academic field seeking to make students the center of the learning process by being able to

demonstrate specific competencies contained in the curriculum. As committing students to participate in projects and initiatives based on the agenda of the social responsibility of the university have an enormous potential to bring multiple benefits to students, teachers, the university and the community as a whole.

2.5. Engaged research

A growing number of academic and practical documents demonstrate growing interest among universities in interacting more directly with communities outside their clusters. This trend can be observed not only in the way they teach their students but also in the research they do. Recent years have shown a progressive shift in their research philosophies as their research has started to reach out and be enriched by more contact with peoples' needs and communities potentials to contribute to the enhancement and use of new knowledge.

According to McDonald (2006) since the 1980's a few science fields including public health, medicine, sociology, social work among others introduced the notion of engagement to their research activities, which has continuously expanded into other fields and disciplines. By year 2000 many more areas of science were considering how their research and their findings should connect to the needs of local communities or communities all around the world. Public health programs represent perhaps the most representative examples, where cases like HIV/AIDS prevention has demonstrated the importance of both objective research and the direct involvement of communities affected by the disease.

This author reflected on how a number of theories contributed to *remolding* the role and the way research is done, in so doing she explains that theories like *empowerment education*, *Community problem solving* and *participatory research* opened doors for traditional research to become more connected to the needs of people and communities they investigate.

By recalling psychologist kurt Lewin as the inventor of the concept of *action research* she describes the interactive process whereby universities engage with communities in the course of identifying and prioritizing social problems, to then together plan and act to solve them. This approach challenged the traditional roles of researchers as external observers and that of subject communities as passive receivers. Instead it proposed the need to *jointly produce new knowledge* from where to channel and direct social changes and policies.

Involving the community in the process of knowledge production contested the traditional roles assigned to the parties and turned observers and subjects into partners, giving a new value to the fact that researchers and communities have different views, which in turn challenged *unscientific knowledge of the communities* making it more valuable and valid.

Among the articles that helped framing our analysis of what social responsibility of the university is in terms of community-engaged research, authors like McDonald (2006) and Fitzgerald (2006) provided enriching and systematic descriptions of what the phenomenon is about and the features that characterize it as a research approach. In a similar way Cooper (n.d.) analyzes the phenomenon from the perspective of interplay of main stakeholders and shows how the typical *triple helix* that connects the university with the industry and the government now is called to include a forth one: the civil society -in terms of its contributions to research both theoretically and practically-.

While articles produced by authors like Whitmer et al. (2010) and Janke & Shelton (2011) offer a more theoretical approach to the issue by defining philosophical aspects of the phenomenon as well as precise terminology and concrete examples of engaged research; these authors coincide in criticizing the traditional attitude of universities and research institutions that focus only on making objective research that is ultimately disconnected with

everyday life and as such remains only theoretical and unable to provide more practical answers to communities' needs. They agree in that through community engaged research universities bring their knowledge and resources out of the classroom and out of campus to enrich scholarship and society.

Authors like Sandmann (n.d.) from a critical perspective analyze the *scientific* implications and challenges of doing engaged research and proposes ways in which difficulties can be solved. While Israel, Schulz, Parker & Becker (2001) provide a description of what the phenomenon of community based participatory research is about but more interestingly they analyze the implications of developing this type of research has in terms of securing necessary funds for sustaining activities, developing partnerships that allow for mutual development of technical capabilities and training while developing policy recommendations.

2.6. Extension and outreach

In this section the review focuses on existing research carried out in the area of extension and outreach. Much of the articles and books analyzed coincide in framing these activities as the *third mission* of the university and include a wide range of initiatives that refer to programs and projects that fall out of the *traditional teaching and researching* that however spill onto society to address some of its problems by using the resources available in the universities or generated by the synergy of the people they bring together.

The literature focuses on three areas, one leaning towards the historical developments of the extension and outreach and how the interactions with society have changed over time, the second portraying cases of projects and programs and the third providing critical views and strategies for improvement and systematization of extension and outreach.

Within the first line for example Tünnermann Bernheim (2000) analyzed how the concept of extension came about as a process in Latin-American higher education and how this process affected and expanded the traditional roles of the university to include new responsibilities and stakeholders, particularly non-academic staff, the students and professors in the decision making process and in the ways the institutions interact with society as a whole.

Although the author focuses on Latin America he sees how that process expanded to affect higher education's role in the world by changing old paternalistic stands of the university before social problems into a more integrated, open and participatory actor in addressing them beyond the provision of knowledge. He analyzes the university in contemporary society where new technologies increase the demands for more interaction between academia and the world outside.

In a similar way but focusing on the current globalized context DeYoung, Harris, & Larsen (1995) analyze the impact new communicational technologies have on universities extension and outreach programs. According to them this context is changing the ways the university interacts with society due to the increased networking capabilities that the internet and other similar technologies brought that facilitate the direct contact of institutions and individuals across the globe regardless of the differences in kinds of audiences and distance; particularly in the case of the universities the article focuses on the extension they can do by *extending* their education clientele upon demand by using networked computing technologies.

In the same line of the authors above Ludwig (1999) and Byrne (2000) analyze the issue of university extension and outreach by looking into the future of the activities universities carry out and how they will interact with communities beyond their immediate location. Although focusing in different aspects these authors coincide in looking at the need to internationalize the work of the university in the area of extension and outreach by analyzing ways in which

universities involve with societies in new ways that increasingly focus on the idea of working together in partnerships rather than unidirectionally as it has traditionally been the case.

They agree in that in the context where universities function today, *engagement* necessarily goes beyond traditional activities of extension and outreach and require new strategies for sharing knowledge, resources and responsibilities in order to bring solutions to some of the society's problems in effective manners that involve all major stakeholders and increasingly integrate the academic work. They both conclude that engagement of the universities with other segments of society will not be an option for universities in the near future, whatever their natures and areas of expertise, be they public or private, social engagement through extension and outreach will be a defining characteristic in regards to what universities do and how they do it, not about whether they do it or not.

Research articles that fall into the second category, that describing practical cases of universities engagement through extension and outreach are quantitatively a clear majority so we will only mention a few representative examples of how research is done in this area.

Hobbs (2004) focused his research on how the nature of the extension and outreach of the universities evolve over time as they address different audiences be it over time or as programs target different communities even if goals and resources may be similar. Although he focuses on the case of how university extension reaches out to first and second generation Latinos in the USA, he finds important trends regarding the challenges extension and outreach encounter as they involve different participants and staff with different cultural and age backgrounds which in turn affects the ways programs are implemented and their outcomes. His research leads him to conclude that new approaches to extension and outreach do not mean the mission of extension and outreach is changing in itself but that universities need to consider these initiatives in ways that allow them to serve new kinds of audiences.

On a different way, in the article named *Externships in Sustainability Program as an Outreach Tool for Extension* Apel, Mostafa, Brandau, & Garfin (2013) provide an enriching view of the history of the phenomenon among American universities in the 20th century; they analyze the concept of *externships* as a form of program where students participate in community-based projects, that in contrast to internships where students shadow other professionals, here externship means that students apply their skills to community outreach by themselves. University extension projects offer undergraduates the space for them to create and conduct their own community projects therefore students are given responsibility for planning, implementing and evaluating their extension work.

These authors argue that as funding for extension programs is always scarce, this strategy leads to searching for cost-effective ways that allow universities to reach out to communities and deliver their programs. And this is what makes externship programs creative and dynamic cost-effective outreach and extension initiatives.

Wolford, Cox, & Culp (2001) analyze the elements that motivate volunteers to join initiatives at the university level. They argue that different kinds of students join and volunteer due to different reasons hence for example, students that become volunteers typically produce connections between those receiving the services and those professionals working at the extension programs of the universities, and this happens through active partnerships. Based on this, information they research on the factors that motivate those students to engage and stay involved. According to their data personal achievements appears as one of the most important reasons why people join and provide social service as volunteers. Other reasons that motivate people to join are having a sense of affiliation, the sense of belonging to a

group that is familiar to them. And lastly other forms of recognition like receiving compliments also appear among the reasons why people volunteer.

In the third line of research we found a number of authors that focus on the challenges universities face when implementing extension and outreach and more importantly some authors provide enriching strategies to overcome those challenges and to move initiatives forward in the search for more effective solutions and better grounded planning.

Examples of this kind of literature include *Where Is Extension Scholarship Falling Short, and What Can We Do About It?* by Alter (2003), who describes main challenges that extension and outreach programs face today reflecting the areas and issues where this form of engagement needs improvement. Alter found that the main shortcomings universities face refer to: 1. Achieving a scholarly mentality; 2. Broadening our view of scholarship as philosophy and concept; 3. Understanding the scholarship of engagement; 4. Conducting research on the scholarship of engagement; 5. Developing and implementing action proposals for change; and 6. Developing tools to assess and document outreach scholarship.

According to this author to address those shortcomings universities account with three ways they can overcome them: action, leadership, and graduate education reform. As a strategy the combination of all three leads the universities to set strategies that serve as guidelines in the ways they interact with society through extension and outreach. In other words, carrying out extension and outreach as key aspects that put the university in contact with the daily problems of the people but in a scholarly manner, which in turn implies that their practice in extension and outreach should be done in such a way that it continues and serves as a provider of research-based solutions to social matters with space for non-formal education.

In a related article Lasley (2008) describes a typical extension activity in terms of how it is created, the actors it involves, the process and products expected as well as ways to evaluate those activities. In his article *The scholarship of extension* he defines it as a creative, rational and systematic inquiry that is both scientific and results in a science based product (typically a kind of service) that is shared with others, however academically subject to peer review and that can be verified and reproduced. In his framework the process of extension activities consider: 1. Who is involved; 2. How the issue is identified; 3. What the university does to address that issue; and 4. What methods the university uses.

All of which leads to a set of products that can be described based on: 1. what products resulted from every engagement activity; 2. How that engagement and its outputs are disseminated and shared; and 3. Considering the usefulness and appreciation of those benefiting from the program and its impact by the receiving and the academic communities.

In their book *Working through Environmental Conflict: The Collaborative Learning Approach* Daniels & Walker (2001) analyze how policy decision making has been changing in different levels and areas which means that increasingly citizens and management personnel seek ways to *do things differently*; which means creating ways to make more stakeholders participate meaningfully in the decision making process. They discuss the theory and technique of collaborative learning and present practical cases where it has been applied to show the implications this approach has for professional life and as a teaching tool for scholars, students, and researchers involved with social and environmental issues.

Archer et al. (2007) provide a framework to analyze extension and outreach to make them effective based on application of a matrix that helps determine the criteria upon which initiatives should be set in their strive for excellence. According to these authors the framework they propose should help universities' extension: 1. Be accountable for the

resources invested; 2. Continually improve the organization's effectiveness; and 3. Describe its strengths and differentiate itself from other agencies and universities.

Lastly among those with more critical views toward the role and relevance of university's extension we found Stephenson's (2003) work that analyzes possible negative effects that university extension and outreach can have upon the populations it may target to serve. The author works on the role of the innovation diffusion theory, which is used as the foundation of extension in agriculture outreach methods. Through the study he shows that even though universities aim to support farmers achieve modern and technological methods of production by disseminating innovation in some cases they actually favored more bigger corporations rather than small size farmers. Because of this he suggests that when universities set themselves to carry out extension and outreach they need to do it from a standpoint that allows them to see well into the future to evaluate the real impacts of their actions.

2.7. Critical views of the social engagement of the university

In spite of the potentials and benefits university engagement brings, there are authors that rise concern from the other side debate on the social responsibility of the universities. Authors like Rhoads (1997) take a rather critical stand on higher education community service. Although he agrees on the idea that learning experiences can be enriched through community involvement of the students he asserts that a critical pedagogy review is still necessary so as to make teachers understand that community service by students should be *instrumental* and not become a means in itself. He criticizes the *pedagogical panacea* that addresses all sorts of problems that seems to be in vogue; the author proposes strategies to help re-think education as a whole and to create pedagogical structures that produce more caring citizens and open to democratic ideals where service learning should serve as a tool.

Bourner (n.d.) also provides a critical view of community engagement by the universities for he argues that these activities do not fit to the notion of a university, as the advancement of knowledge while the main goal of community engagement is to make students use some of the university's specialized assets, such as its intellectual riches, teaching abilities, access to networks and learning groups, in ways that benefit the community – meaning that those activities are *peripheral* to the core business of the university- and *that* increases risks of diverting resources away from its main goal.

Also from a critical perspective Muijen (2004) analyzes social responsibility in terms of *value-learning processes* implemented in the context of The Netherlands. The author argues that the incorporation of social responsibility in organizations of all kinds cannot be accomplished by forcing people to comply with norms but rather, for an effective implementation strategies need to be supported with a transformation at the culture level of the organization. In line with this she proposes that cultural changes in any organization should be based on dialogue and innovation in the curricula and the primary processes of education.

A problem rises as institutions need to decide for a priority in ethical/strategic terms, meaning that they need to translate into practical activities concepts that should remain scientific. Hence institutions face the need to face an hypothesis according to which institutionalizing an adequate context for life-long (value) learning may serve to counterbalance the process of rationalization and where an ethical–didactical approach is required creating a dilemma in terms of achieving practical implementation of ethical reflection in universities without becoming too moralistic or too instrumental. The contradiction lies in the fact that universities may become fundamentalist in their ideals becoming a threat to other cultures.

She analyzes the case of globalized Dutch universities that are constantly being revised through the glass of authentic openness to multi-culturalism and multi-ethnicity.

Weerts (2005) analyzes some cases of projects that were initiated in different universities in the United States and provides a description of how typically relations between universities and communities may evolve over time and become difficult and conflictive. Through his research he showed that in cases where universities take part in community programs, they tend to become self-centered and even autocratic, a trend that seems to reappear specially in moments like the decision of the topic to be addressed, proceedings, schedules and so forth. Based on data gathered for the study, he argues that many people in a project may actually feel foreign to it as decisions and implementation may neglect them altogether if the university is too central to the project.

2.8. Observations on the literature

Through the previous pages the review described the main areas where research has taken place on the engagement of the university with the problems of the community through cooperative solutions. By analyzing the debates around university social responsibility and about the role of the university the review provides a justification to the need to further analyze the phenomenon by looking at its underlying mission: providing and generating knowledge while at the same time producing graduates and citizens that are caring, sensitive, proactive and efficient professionals, hence working as an agent for positive social change.

To counter balance an evident excess of positive perceptions, the review provides areas where social responsibility of the university still remains a debatable issue and areas where critical thinking and further theoretical development are still needed in terms of *how things should work* once universities decide to embark on socially responsible initiatives.

An important observation to be done from the review is the intrinsic connection that exists among the traditional roles of the university, research done on the topic demonstrate that although teaching and researching are unquestionable tasks of any university, it also shows that universities cannot remain as impermeable bubbles to the communities around them. And that by implementing initiatives with a high content of social responsibility universities can improve and even boost their traditional roles by making the learning process not only more effective but also more humane.

Even if social engagement of the university may appear to some critics as a risk in diverting valuable resources of the university toward goals that *fall out of its scope*, the review suggests that universities, students and societies have more to win from this cooperative endeavors.

The fact that communications and technologies are advancing at such a speed put both universities and communities in closer touch, which calls for more and renewed interactions. However, how are those interactions to happen? What are the best ways in which universities can cooperate with their communities? What is the ultimate role of the university in regards to the problems that affect their societies? It is clear that universities cannot afford to stay isolated and that engaging with societies brings positive changes to both sides of the relation... but, how can those relations be defined and promoted?

These are some of the questions this research will try to answer in the upcoming pages.

3. Methodology

3.1. Context and overview

The present research took place in the context of the *Foreign Research Fellowship Visit* program at Tsukuba University in 2013 and represents the results from approaching the issue of social responsibility of the university in a comprehensive way.

3.2. Research questions

Given the variety of issues that fall in social responsibility of the university the study approaches the topic first in terms of why and how universities engage their resources and energy in work that is considered *responsible* before society.

To do it two areas of interest were identified and researched, the first refers to *what social responsibly of the university* is and relates to descriptors that characterize the phenomenon; and the second focuses on *interactions of the university with society* that refers to the ways in which universities relate with the communities where they exist and function.

Within this context the research questions guiding the study were organized into two groups responding to the above areas as follows:

1. *What is social responsibly of the university?*

- What characterizes the phenomenon?
- What motivates a university to engage into addressing social problems?
- What elements define social engagement of the university?
- What role do other stakeholders have? And how do they interact?
- What benefits can be expected when universities act as socially responsible agents and promoters of social change?

2. *What interactions between university and society materialize social responsibility?*

- What are the areas where universities act as agents of social change?
- What are the academic benefits of social engagement for the university?
- What is service learning?
- How does the university act responsibly when creating new knowledge? Or what is engaged research?
- What is the nature of extension and outreach in terms of social responsibility?
- What is the role of a university's management in setting an institutional direction toward social responsibility?

3.3. Nature of the study

The study describes the problem of social responsibility of the university based on a review of articles that portray and analyze it from different perspectives so as to integrate alternative views into an overall and inclusive assessment of what social responsibility of the university means, what benefits it brings to society and the academic community through interactions that address problems affecting their communities.

The research was set looking at a global level by including articles describing the phenomenon coming from all continents in order to describe it; and to show that similar trends can be observed in totally different geographical contexts.

3.4. Goals & objectives

Goals:

- Contribute to the understanding of social responsibility of the university by describing what motivates universities to engage in socially responsible behaviors and to better understand its nature, dimensions and forms.
- Analyze the question of whether social responsibility of the university is a moral call for action to assist those in need of a few individuals, or if it is something embedded – yet not always realized- in the mission of higher education institutions.
- Promote the implementation of new social projects, where universities can engage on the solution of practical matters of their communities based on that understanding.
- Describe what the phenomenon is about, what elements typically conform it and how social responsibility of the university works.
- Promote a deeper sense of responsibility among universities by demonstrating that they contribute to social development by using their resources in alternative ways through their interactions with the rest of the social tissue.

Objectives

- Describe motivations that drive universities to act as socially responsible agents.
- Portray what acting as a socially responsible university means according to different interactions of the university with society.
- Describe ways in which universities understand the concept and how they canalize that into action.
- Provide an overview about the areas where universities typically commit.
- Describe benefits expected from the social engagement of the universities.
- Explore the connections between the notions of service learning, engaged research, extension and outreach, management and social responsibility.
- Spot good practices and examples.

3.5. Research focus

This research analyzes motivations and procedures carried out at the university level aimed at improving the quality of life of people by carrying out activities that overflow traditional academic work. As such this study focuses on:

- Motivations at the university to design and implement socially responsible actions.
- Strategies used to identify social needs to be addressed and the strategies followed to design, implement and evaluate those activities.
- Policy and mechanisms set by universities to transform themselves as entities that cultivate not only human resources, but most importantly socially sensitive and committed graduates.

3.6. Scope of the research

The research focuses on social responsibility of universities at the global level by looking at experiences taking place in the following areas:

- At the institutional level
- At the community involvement level; and
- At the campus life level.

3.7. Method

The study analyzes social responsibility of the universities based on previous research and other antecedents by looking at the bases upon which it is constructed among universities across the world and then by analyzing the strategies universities use to design and implement activities that address some of the social issues they perceive as important by engaging in activities and partnerships that go beyond their traditional academic roles.

The study analyzes how social responsibility is included in the academic formation of the students in order to provide them with real life experiences in a way to pedagogically support their learning process. In so doing this research is largely based on the premises of theories like the critical social theory and social constructivism as points from where socially responsible activities are designed and implemented as a model for academic formation and social transformation.

A number of socially responsible initiatives implemented by some universities were taken as examples to support the theory presented in the points above regarding ways in which universities in different parts of the world implement programs in the strive to act as socially responsible agents.

3.8. Data collection

Data were gathered through an extensive online search using engines like Google Scholar, Yahoo Research and the web based program Mendeley.

The search was done on combinations of targeted terms such as *social responsibility of the university, university engagement, higher education third role, students' social engagement, service learning, engaged research, University extension and outreach, and Responsible university management.*

The initial search resulted in a large number of articles that were organized in thematic areas for further reduction and integration; they included:

- Anecdotic information and experiences of universities on socially responsible activities
- Theoretical aspects and analysis by researchers and practitioners of the phenomenon

3.9. Data analysis

Descriptive and comparative approaches were applied to integrate data from sources into a unified body. Firstly research articles and other sources were classified into five categories:

- General descriptors of social responsibility of the university
- Descriptors on service learning
- Descriptors on engaged research
- Descriptors on extension and outreach, and
- Descriptors on management and administration

Information relevant for each category from different articles was extracted and then integrated with other pieces of similar value, because of this some of the articles utilized contributed to different parts of the research.

Following the research questions information gathered for each category was distributed into the following two sections, chapter four analyzing *what social responsibly of the university is;* and chapter 5 describing *interactions between university and society that demonstrate social responsibility.*

4. Defining social responsibility of the university

This chapter describes social responsibility of the university, however given the complexity of the issue, the coming pages provide an overview that combines data from the literature review to portray it based on aspects that delineate what it is, how it works, its benefits, the role of the stakeholders and other illustrative aspects.

The literature examined shows that typically authors associate social responsibility with a positive or negative judgment attached to the impacts that decisions and actions have on the societies they relate to. Hence the next step of this research is analyzing the ways in which the university relates to society (teaching, research, extension and outreach, and management) and how social responsibility can be observed in each of these areas.

4.1. Motivations: Why do universities engage?

Analyzing the motivations behind universities' engagement in the solution of social problems help us approach the problem of *what social responsibility of the university is* because this provides indicators to understand what drives people in the universities to participate in projects and initiatives that absorb part of their resources into activities that may fall out of their traditional duty, hence showing the initial elements of nature of the phenomenon.

Recent decades have shown an increasing interest among social players on the need to manage organizations in more rational and responsible ways, meaning that management of social organisms has to go beyond their internal logics and goals to widen their scopes and have more inclusive views of the organizations in relation to the context where they function.

Research on social responsibility in general and the increasing institutionalization of the social responsibility of the private sector show growing interest among different kinds of institutions wishing to act as engaged agents; the same can be observed in other areas, as it happens in *socially responsible investment* among financiers and economists; *socially responsible consumption* among buyers; or *socially responsible territories* for local governments. This trend suggests a loop of mutual promotion of responsible attitudes and benefits where as organizations seek to act responsibly researchers are promoting more forms of engagement and more efficient ways to do it.

Peralta Portillo (2011) asserts that social responsibility is usually described and explained by the Kantian glasses of social virtue, where individuals (and social bodies as associations of individuals) are expected to freely conceive and accept the universal *maxims* of our behaviors. This means that people normally act in ways that at a minimum consider whether the effects of those actions are compatible with the permanence and development of human life.

An interesting aspect to be noted is that there are different sources from where this attitude may spur, such as pure enterprise philanthropy or social benevolence, it also relates to labor claims, ecological activism, protection of human rights or fair trade among many others. The interesting common thread here is that it calls for commitment and action that, however, in the case of the universities include special features.

Similar to the social responsibility of private sector, increasing number of universities see that not only they have the potential to contribute to the betterment of their communities but also see the need to commit their efforts towards the betterment of peoples' lives in ways that comprise initiatives that go beyond their traditional academic work.

Universities may take different attitudes towards their communities, which determine the kind, scope and level of interactions they have; they may opt to behave passively responsible by avoiding to carry out activities that bring harmful effects to the rest of the community. In a

way this attitude reflects organizations that work on their own world as encapsulated entities that only seek to minimize negative social effects their work may have.

Other universities instead actively engage with their communities, committing to activities that explicitly aim to improve the conditions of those living there and dynamically use the resources they account with in order to bring social changes out of their potentials. When universities actively embark on socially responsible behaviors they do it seeking to achieve standards that reveal the values upon which they are built, values that speak of creating citizens that are sensitive, proactive, inclusive and democratic; and values that speak of the role universities have as agents of social change.

Ayuso & Sasia Santos (2008) believe that universities too, as any other social organization, have a moral obligation to behave according to the Kantian principle of *you must, then you can*, which by the nature of the university itself should not work as paternalistic consideration or as simple social charity but as an engaged actor that is actually a beneficiary of the changes it promotes and the outcomes those changes produce.

The active engagement materializes in activities that relate to an ethical attitude of the universities that feel a moral call to act before society and its needs; it can also relate to an ideology with which the university agrees, which makes people therein feel obliged to act and contribute in the improvements of the conditions of the community where they are inserted.

The above implies that through this kind of initiatives universities strive for social harmony, to promote forms of development that are sustainable and to improve the quality of life of those related to it by keeping the balance overtime of social, ecological and economic conditions.

From a different perspective, social responsibility of the university relates to a normative call implying that through actions universities materialize values that are dear to the managers, teachers and students. According to Peralta Portillo, these refer to values needed to create pacific and productive lives in any society, like the promotion of freedom and human dignity, constructive citizenship, democracy, solidarity towards others, etc.; and to principles upon which universities build their mission in search of truth and academic excellence.

Peralta Portillo argues that projects where universities engage to respond to the problems of their communities reveal the identity of the universities, *they show who universities are. It is the engagement with its surrounding communities what tells who the university wants to be, believes to be, actually is and does*; while at the same time, these initiatives evidence what communities expect (get or do not get) from the higher education institutions.

In a similar way Peric (2012) explains that universities behave as socially responsible entities to show that *they know* and that *they can respond to social issues* through projects related to community development and educational programs that educate students to be responsible and contribute to their communities with positive changes. Responsibility materializes in universities developing educational programs that prepare students for their professional careers and for active participation in activities that bring social improvements.

Acting socially responsible means acting in ways that are integrative and open, that are inspirational and that motivate people to do things they normally would not otherwise do, hence social responsibility of the university aims at integrating social players in the search for responses to common issues based on personal and institutional interests and motivations.

These efforts relate to the universities' own missions in cases where, for example medicine students volunteer in natural disasters; or where institutions committed to the formation of teachers take part in projects preparing educators by committing their efforts to teach marginalized communities like in refugee camps or providing education services to minorities excluded from main stream channels.

In some cases these initiatives relate to research goals of the universities as they commit to activities that benefit communities while profiting from those activities to generate new knowledge, for example as a group of biology students mobilize local rural areas to raise awareness on the risk of diseases like dengue fever or malaria while carrying out research on indigenous ways to prevent infection or effectiveness of medicines being used.

In other cases, academic personnel or students commit and mobilize efforts and resources to assist communities in need out of the ethical motivation *to do something useful*. Examples of this may include students mobilizing resources to support a school in a poor community; or professors coordinating activities to support communities of foreigners living in their cities.

The analysis of the literature and the projects revised show that in all cases the *justification* universities use to explain their socially responsible activities typically relate to aspects like direct technical contributions and expertise from the university towards the economic and social development of local communities, the promotion of human rights, the protection of the environment, among many other socially relevant goals.

In this sense Gaete Quezada (2010) defines university engagement as a *transformational call* that refers to the need people feel towards being a part of the changes and solutions they perceive as necessary toward social betterment. Which once again, in the case of the universities has a particular significance since most universities perceive themselves as institutions that have an inherent responsibility to lead other stakeholders in society to reflect and develop ways that, by joining their efforts, can reach better living standards and create societies that are fair, clean and sustainable.

In the case of general motivations to engage the university typically functions as a unifying center, a forum for the creation of synergy; this stand point is a key element that gives the university a renewed social role that is in essence more proactive rather than being a simple external detached observer of the social realities that surround life in campus.

Among more practical motivations we found researchers like Furko & Billig (2001) analyzing why universities involve in social initiatives; they assert that educational institutions carry out social programs responding to motivations that include:

1. Reducing the involvement of student risk behaviors by learning critical thinking and problem solving;
2. Promoting participation and constructive attitudes toward formal education and their mates while promoting ethical attitudes and caring for others;
3. Increasing awareness about careers' goals and procedures, increasing exposure to real life experiences and improving their academic achievements;
4. Improving students' development and social skills while deepening their knowledge and understanding about their communities, which in turn leads to looking at ways in which they can contribute and become active members of their communities; and
5. Facing grass root community needs and foster relations between educational institutions and surrounding communities.

4.2. University resources

The above reveals that motivations behind the attitudes of those promoting social changes from the universities are varied and that they may lead to ramifications that bring innovative answers to different aspects of the social dynamics as newer forms of behaviors are purposely encouraged through responsible decisions from different actors.

The literature analyzed suggests that what motivates the universities to engage is typically inherent to their own mission and is based on the realization of people working there about the potentials these institutions have to contribute to their communities, which takes us back to the Kantian moral obligation people feel to bring potentials into action.

Universities have a unique kind of power that lies on the legitimacy societies give to them based on their mission and position within the social tissue. Together with this *soft power*, they have other forms of *power* that give them a key comparative advantage to promote social change: their capacity to assemble different human resources within and outside their cadres, their networking capacities and their traditional academic authority.

Including social responsibility in the structures of universities means creating commitments and creating *passions* among people. These activities usually raise ethical awareness about the need to bring answers to some of the problems societies face, sometimes as palliatives, and sometimes by finding and addressing the root causes of those problems. Universities can by their own nature mobilize and organize people and resources, engaging them in alternative activities beyond their traditional goals.

The literature reviewed suggests an increasing trend among universities to institutionalize these initiatives; which can be observed, for example, in the fact that social responsibility is incorporated into the philosophical base upon which universities function.

The list and nature of initiatives of this sort are extensive, and regardless of the particularities, they all offer important information regarding the potentials and authority universities have to create networks and to mobilize alternative resources toward social good. Universities account with a unique set of potentials that relate to their reason of existence: production and dissemination of knowledge; as such they can offer direction and guidance to society.

4.3. Think responsible, act responsible

As we saw in the literature review, not always good intentions lead to good outcomes, therefore the need to deep and seriously consider how university engagements work and the probable outcomes they can produce. When universities engage with their communities they consider the conditions that make that commitment feasible into a responsible option; this means that for them to act responsibly in their engagements with society they need to first *think responsibly* so as to have a clear vision of how the commitment will work.

This includes considering what resources the university has, its networking capabilities, the level of acceptance and support from other stakeholders it can expect and the projections of the project into a sustainable future. In other words, before actually committing itself into a socially responsible initiative any university needs to make sure that *that engagement* is consistent with its own mission and capabilities; that *that engagement* goes beyond personal or organizational impulses to assume the role of a social transformer to be a structural element that defines who the university is and wants to be.

Some research has been done in this regard by Ayuso & Sasía Santos (2008) who explained that for universities to responsibly commit in addressing social problems they need to, at least, consider three basic conditions that may limit their capabilities through the process of implementation of the projects *before* it is actually launched. These refer to:

- Sustainability of the university's support to the project;
- A proper analysis of the context of the university and the community it addresses; and
- Its actual capacity to respond to the demands society may expect from it.

According to these authors universities need to ensure that the support they offer will be sustained over time until goals are reached or through the end of the project when that can be envisioned. They assert that a university that honestly decides to take part in the solution of a given social problem must first be able to guaranty that its commitment is institutional and not based on personal wishes or philanthropic rushes related to universities' directors desire to promote their image; instead a responsible commitment needs to be reliable, hence that the university must feel and act as a *partner*, and as such it needs to understand that it has an obligation toward the project resulting from the university's structure as a whole.

Contextualization refers the need to consider that even if all universities share a number of goals and features, they are all different due to their structures, dimensions, resources, capabilities and also as the context where they work. Hence not all university commitments to addressing social problems can be the same. The context determines the scope and capability of a university to engage and a responsible understanding of this context is a basic element of the success of the project. This relates to issues such as general level of development where the university works, security conditions, legal restrictions, etc.

The response capability of a university relates to the fact that the decision of universities to engage as an agent for social change, must be done upon the acknowledgment that not all universities account with the capability to commit in as much as they would like in solving some social problems. This implies that nobody should assume that because a university engages to contribute to the solution of a problem it automatically means the university accounts with enough resources, knowledge and experience on the topic so as to guaranty that the outcomes from that engagement will necessarily be positive and significant.

To the points above, Gander (2009) adds that universities need to account with the necessary academic freedom to make their decisions and interact with the reality of their communities based on solid understanding of their virtues and limitations. Being academically free means that academic personnel engaged with socially responsible projects must account with the necessary space and resources to pursue their work without ideological interferences.

In practical terms this means that universities need to direct their members to perform on that commitment making it general enough so as to be able of addressing the issues they are expected to address and specific enough so as to be able to identify individuals that are both willing and able to perform the required tasks of the project. This relates to both the goals of the research universities do and the ways in which they set their curricula so as to produce objective outcomes and promote independent thinking among the students and teachers.

Another important issue universities need to consider when planning the implementation of socially responsible initiatives relates to the challenge they face to ensure that the people leading the projects will commit to its goals and procedures within a time frame that is long enough to achieve the goals, while also ensuring commitment to avoid risks that changes of personnel may bring to the continuity and direction of projects.

4.4. University interactions: partnerships and other stakeholders

4.4.1. Level of university partnerships

Universities commit in responsible initiatives in different levels; engagements happen at local, national, regional or global levels, depending on the scope of activities and the partners with whom they collaborate. In most cases the local level is the paramount as they portray the more *intimate* linkages universities have, where partnerships include both inter-institutional but most importantly inter-personal relations upon which the partnerships develop.

The connection university-community can also take root and generate changes as they synthesize and jointly workout interests at national and international levels. In this sense Marginson & Rhoades (2012) note that in recent years in the discourse of university social engagement there is increasing use of vocabulary referring to *glocal* or *glonacal* approaches to social responsibility, implying a growth in the kind and level of interactions universities have with different communities outside their traditional scopes.

Vallaey (2009) has pointed out that social responsibility of the university entails activities that invite multiple actors -other than universities themselves- to compromise and commit their energies and resources in projects that integrate into an agreed strategy perspectives and views of all those involved in the problem and its solution (direct and indirectly related).

4.4.2. Nature of partnerships

The literature analyzed shows that partnerships between universities and other stakeholders in the communities are born and develop based on:

1. Visions that different parties share about some common purposes;
2. The fact that they may have compatible interests;
3. They may perceive that different realities complement each other; and
4. They may hold the view of future common prospects.

Interestingly even if the combination of these factors and the specific contents of each of them determine different contexts and possibilities for partnership, and even if they account with different modes of governance, responsibilities and resources, still the element that combines these variables into functional partnerships is the fact that decisions about the direction of the projects are usually made jointly (although reasonably with different levels of engagement and responsibility of the different players).

In most of the articles analyzed we found that the process of engaging other partners typically shows the interest from the universities to democratize the decision making process of those initiatives to bring in the contributions from the partners while challenging traditional egocentric views of the universities.

A key fact observed here is that in most cases universities promote engagement with the community to make local people a fundamental partner in the diagnosis, design and implementation of initiatives towards the solution of their problems. These engaging strategies speak of the search for participatory commitments that not only allow, but more importantly promote a sense of ownership among those affected by the projects.

Even if communities and universities may work as partners, not all alliances function the same way, relations can be smooth or rather bumpy, they can allow for equal participation or for more unbalanced distribution of inputs and benefits, etc. Based on the differences among kinds of interaction Gander (2009) developed a typology of partnerships, where the relations between the university with the community can be classified as *consultative*; *technical assistance*; *convenience*; *generative*; *mutual benefit*; and *outreach*. Clearly the nature and content of each of these relations varies according to how the university sees itself interacting with other stakeholders and how those initiatives are designed and implemented.

4.4.3. Constructive relations

All relations a university has to other social partners have specific features and are based on factors that contribute to the workability of those relations. In order to provide a positive guidance to universities wishing to establish cooperative partnerships that are efficient,

productive and durable with other social organizations Gander suggests that those relations should be based on shared features that include:

1. Common functions and compatible philosophies
2. Shared governance responsibilities
3. Documentation and accountability
4. Time and patience
5. Dealing with different priorities

1. Common functions and compatible philosophies imply that the deeper the connection of the program to the goals of the university, faculty or department the higher the chances the commitment to the project will remain firm; this is because when goals of projects overlap with goals of the educational programs, teachers and students have more to gain and are happier to commit more energy to it. The same can be expected from community members, as the more they feel the project brings benefits to their lives, the more they support it and feel as the owners of the project, hence the higher the chances they will remain committed.

2. Shared governance responsibilities. Distribution of tasks and responsibilities as well as devolution and transfer of governance of the project is a major area of interaction. Deciding who does what and how the benefits and costs are distributed includes practical and political decisions that need attention throughout the whole life of any project.

Some times projects evolve to bring in new participants or transfer their management to leaders in the community, to other agencies or institutions or even to the university itself. When this happens parties to the project need to handle that transfer with care as these transitions may carry important risks to the continuation of the project. Potential challenges relate to implications of the change to those involved; there may be legal or financial procedures to be followed that may have important complexity and responsibility.

Changes in the structure or direction of any project should, whenever possible, be foreseen and set to avoid conflict. A good policy to protect the sustainability of a project is to include mechanisms to avoid and deal with disagreement and mediation, should conflicts arise.

3. Documentation and accountability. Maintaining records of decisions, processes, resources and outcomes is a positive measure to ensure communication, tractability and accountability.

From the perspective of the learning experience, it is considered a good practice that partners and particularly students are encouraged to keep records and notes throughout the process including data they use, learning outcomes from the process, the same goes for other forms of information that can help support the learning process such as results from interviews, personal or institutional motivations, ideas, reactions, decisions and evaluations.

4. Time and Patience. Designing and developing projects, agreeing terms and conditions, allocating and distributing resources, assigning tasks and responsibilities require efforts from all parties. Work to plan, agree and implement the project requires patience and goodwill; it is unrealistic to think that everything will always go smooth; each project has its own cycle and evolves in its own way, hence keeping this in mind to all parties is a priority.

5. Dealing with different priorities. Competing interests of parties to a project are elements to consider at all times. They set direction and speed in which resources are allocated and the outcomes expected. A common hassle here is that university members and community leaders may have different prerogatives, for example as teachers seek to boost the learning experiences of the students, community leaders may be more concerned on solutions to their problems or even campaigning for political visibility. Gaps in priorities of the stakeholders will affect agendas, timelines and decisions, as well as outputs from the project.

4.4.4. Possible areas of tension

The literature suggests that in most cases where universities and communities engage on common ventures, they typically are expensive enterprises in terms of financial resources and the *price* of including the outflow of valuable resources, especially time and energy. Decisions on how those resources are to be funded, allocated and distributed can become thorny issues that may put in risk the whole project if they are not dealt properly.

While also the issue of effective leadership and the division of tasks are central parts of the life of the projects, there is always the need to determine lines of command and decision, and ways to deal with the leadership of the project. In many cases relations can be prosperous and easily move forward; however there are times in which things may not be so smooth, it is then central for these projects to account with people in key roles that are able to lead all the members and parties towards agreed goals.

Matters of this sort may bring conflict especially when academics tend to have a vision that is determined by their own formation, however at the community levels the mottos for actions, motivations and way things are done or expected to happen, are typically very different.

4.4.5. Stakeholders

As mentioned, social responsibility of the university refers to ways the higher education institutions interact with other organizations and communities in activities or projects that include but go beyond the traditional roles of the university: teaching and researching.

Hence if we are considering *interactions*, then clearly we are talking of *other partakers* in these relations; the notion of *responsibility* itself carries the inherent idea of at least two parts of a relationship. However, when we are talking about *social responsibility of the university...* Who are we talking about? Who are those other parties the university interacts with? And how do they help us understand the nature of the phenomenon?

Gaete Quezada (2011) and Vallaey (2009) identify kinds of stakeholders in relationships based on the impacts and effects those initiatives generate. The classification they propose separates stakeholders as active and passive actors depending on their roles, where active ones represent those in charge of designing, implementing and evaluating projects, as opposed to those described as net recipients and beneficiaries of the activities, hence rather passive. In practice however this distinction may be blurry as the active parts may also profit direct and indirectly from the activities, while those considered recipients or passive may in fact, also contribute to the changes sought and to the development of the activities, even if in ways that are less explicit yet not less important.

Following Gaete Quezada we find that based on the roles different parts to a project have stakeholders typically include: 1. Personnel at the universities (teaching and non-teaching); 2. Researchers; 3. University authorities; 4. Students; 5. Providers; 6. Graduates; 7. Employers; 8. Competitors; 9. Local communities; 10. Social organizations; and 11. The state. To which we could add 12. The international community.

4.5. Benefits and contributions

When universities decide to act responsibly and implement projects or behave in ways that are socially responsible, these initiatives usually bring along effects that benefit the academic community within the university as well as other communities outside campus.

Social responsibility of the university refers to the impacts and effects its actions produce. From here it follows that universities wishing to be responsible set themselves to produce

social benefits from the efforts they do in whatever their forms. Hence, for instance these efforts relate to the setting of responsible campuses, the provision of education and formation that is socially sensitive and responsible towards the production of engaged citizens, the social management of knowledge and democratic and open participation.

Socially responsible activities are associated with the creation of spaces for cooperation and projects that can produce win-win benefits to both local as well as academic communities.

The underlying assumption in efforts of this kind is that universities can contribute not only directly in whatever their goals but also to the socialization process of the students and personnel by providing them with values and venues to acquire values that are dear to their societies, values that will then be brought back and replicated into society as graduates and future members of the productive systems and local communities.

Research done on engagement of the university show that these programs produce outcomes that exceed academic goals of the universities. According to Gaete Quezada, for example, at least four possible types of repercussions can be expected when universities implement projects that incorporate social responsible elements; the author classifies them as:

1. Organizational repercussions
2. Educative repercussions
3. Cognitive repercussions
4. Social repercussions

a. *Organizational repercussions* represent outcomes from projects happening internal and externally at the institutional level. Within the university effects are observed, for instance, when projects are designed to improve working conditions for the personnel at the university, or when universities provide better learning conditions through infrastructure and facilities. While *externally* effects can be seen, for example, in the environmental impact of university activities in and outside campus, or through engagements of the university with the problems of their communities.

b. *Educative repercussions*, relate to the kind of professionals universities generate as a result of the formation provided and activities that require the engagement of staff, students and teachers outside traditional academia. Here, repercussions relate to the pedagogic process through which teaching and learning happens, while seeking to give graduates a formation that is integral and that contributes to the wellbeing of the community beyond the formation of professionals by creating *sensitive citizens*.

c. *Cognitive repercussions* refer to the impacts universities generate when they engage with their communities to bring about solutions to problems affecting them by creating new knowledge and carrying out engaged research that is relevant in substance and purpose. Typical examples of this include action research projects born out of the university to bring desirable and positive changes in their communities.

d. *Social repercussions* include impacts universities produce as they engage in the promotion of social changes by participating in projects toward social development and the resolution of social problems, by producing social capital and making knowledge available to society.

Other authors like Viteri-Moya, Jácome-Villacres & Medina-León (2013) coincide with the ideas proposed above and assert that when universities engage in socially responsible programs they also generate other effects that relate to:

a. *Environmental effects* that are caused by the daily activities of the university, both within and outside campus and through all of their activities; and

b. *Communicational effects* that refer to how universities relate to the community in providing, receiving and processing information on projects and their effects. This also refers to channels in which activities and outcomes are communicated to stakeholders affected.

According to these authors the communicational aspect is a crucial part of the live of any socially responsible project -even if many times they may be neglected- as it is through these effects that monitoring and accountability take place, hence relating to the sustainability and final ownership of the projects by all related stakeholders.

Specifically in terms of pedagogical benefits that the implementation of programs that are socially responsible bring to the universities are those that relate more intimately with the mission of the university, in this regard two authors have made interesting contributions.

Gie (2007) analyzed how service learning as a teaching methodology is used by universities to enhance students' interpersonal skills and the appreciation of cultural diversity; the author suggests that implementing these programs develop the students' professional learning experiences, as well as their corporate social responsibility as through the process they are encouraged to reflect on their learning experiences, both academic and personally. Her research proposes that the application of service learning at the university level develops students as future *corporate citizens*, thereby contributing to sustainable socio-economic development in communities and society at large.

While Mills (2004) asserts that socially responsible policies of universities promote effective teaching and learning as institutions develop more coherent practices that demonstrate and materialize the institution's values through interactions with real life situations.

This author argues that while it is easy to imagine how academics and students in some disciplines (like economics or history) can contribute to community-university interaction, it is more difficult to imagine how those in more theoretical disciplines (such as mathematics or physics) can be involved, however he explains that, even if it is true that these academics contribute to the local community through their teaching and research, they can also contribute in alternative ways where they can use their research skills to help communities. In this sense and according to Mills even the most abstract disciplines have ways and potentials to contribute to the betterment of society.

5. University social responsibility in action

In chapter four we analyzed the general theory behind the concept of social responsibility of the university, this gives us a general framework to understand what the phenomenon is about, in the pages to come we will focus instead on the areas where that responsibility can be observed; this concretely refers to the interaction that universities have with society, basically through: teaching, research, extension and outreach and management.

5.1. Service learning

Quantitatively speaking an important part of the literature points at the fact university social responsibility usually colligates one of the inherent roles of the university (teaching) with activities that bring positive changes to society while exposing the students to learning experiences based on real life interactions; this is commonly known as *service learning*.

According to Peric (2012) the expression *service learning* was first developed in 1967 by Robert Sigmon and William Ramsey upon which later Honnet and Poulsen (1989) developed the service learning model and set of *Principles of Good Practice in Combining Service and Learning* that serve as the most general theoretical framework.

Service learning is understood as a method that allows students to acquire knowledge, apply what they know and to develop skills by actively participating in academically designed experiences of service aimed at meeting actual community needs and that are carried out as the result from cooperation between universities and the communities where they function.

More specifically, the term refers to a particular goal some universities set for themselves in some of their programs as they design and implement projects within their study platforms seeking to benefit the community outside campus and students; typically these programs materialize in activities where the community receives a service it needs, while students systematically learn *in* and *from* the process while providing those services.

Henao Aguirre (2010, p.49) defines service learning as:

“Course-based, credit bearing educational experience in which students: a) participate in an organized service activity that meets identified community goals [needs]; and b) reflect on the service activity in such a way as to gain further understanding of course content, a broader appreciation of the discipline, and an enhanced sense of civic responsibility.”

While Gie (2007, p.19) delineates the concept in saying that

“SL [service learning] transforms students from passive knowledge-seeking individuals, to active socially-responsible citizens of a country.”

According to this author -and by citing CHE: HEQC Criteria for Institutional Audits (2004)- the main feature of these programs is the reciprocity, where all parts in the relation obtain something from each other, as the engagement to serve becomes a part of the curriculum required to the students. In this sense, service learning is seen as a strategy that offers better chances for success and sustainability over time to socially responsible projects and to students that can apply in practice what they learn in the classrooms; therefore both parts in the relation mutually profit from it.

Given the nature of the term, some authors provide interesting distinctions that differentiate it with other related, yet different expressions.

Gie notes differences between *community engagement* and *service learning* in saying that the first concept refers to projects and processes in which universities compromise their know-

how and other resources to address relevant issues to their communities. This means that community engagement materializes in ways that include activities that fall within a wide fan comprising informal and unstructured activities, as well as formal and structured academic programs designed to respond to the demands and needs of a community. The second concept -service learning- instead looks at the engagement of the universities from a scholarly approach, hence putting the focus on the development of the students as future citizens.

Gie also distinguishes service learning from *Volunteer activities*; which emphasize on the benefits obtained by the target community as a result from the participation and services provided by students and institutions. Typically, volunteer activities are not part of the student's curricula; hence they do not contribute to the accumulation of credits towards graduation. The level of involvement of the institutions varies but because they tend to rely more on personal motivations their sustainability over time may be hampered easily.

Service learning is also different from *community outreach*, which refers to activities that focus on the target community as the main beneficiary while seeking to promote the learning process of the students through the provision of services. Usually initiatives of this sort are born from faculties or departments in the university and have clearer structures and goals, where activities and commitment from the students may be regulated, evaluated and recognized in the form of academic credits or be considered for publication of research.

Internship programs defer from service learning in that the first see the student as the main receiver, where the learning process and its outcomes represent the primary goal. These educational activities offer students opportunities to experience and develop vocational and practical skills, while deepening their understanding of real world interactions, they may or may not be related to their main area of study.

And lastly, service learning is different from *cooperative education* in that the latter focus on learning outcomes of the student (not the community) as the beneficiary from the activities. These initiatives enhance students' understanding of their field of study by participating in activities that help them compare educational experiences in different settings. For example as students are placed and work in industries that are related to their careers.

Research carried out by Dana Moore Gray (in Cunliff & Barthell, 2011) suggests a growing number of teachers and practitioners utilizing service learning in their educational programs based on the idea that this strategy generates win-win outcomes, where both students learn by putting the knowledge and skills they have into practice as they work in the real world. While at the same time these activities provide communities with services that are beneficial to them in a form of extra and cheap (if not for free) assistance. In so doing this practices become a form of experiential education combined with structured pedagogical programs that promote formal learning and practical social development.

5.1.1. Nature of the phenomenon

Through an extensive review Wentzel (1991) reflects on the interdependent nature of the two phenomena -social responsibility of the university and service learning-; this author concludes that both concepts interact in the context of formal educational settings and are typically set seeking to shape the social and cognitive behaviors of students.

When universities design programs that contain service learning elements they do it based on the belief that they can contribute toward society's improvement, hence the socially responsible aspect of the engagement.

Even if concretely speaking initiatives in each field are different due to their settings, goals, participants and contexts, they all share a few common elements that characterize them:

- a) They are set on a pedagogic approach based on the assumption that serving others within an academic program offers extra value to the learning experience and promotes a deeper and personal reflection among students in terms of what has been learnt.
- b) They seek to systematically integrate formal and non-formal learning experiences with the needs of the community through service.
- c) They promote cooperation between partners in different social realms where community and academy come to work together for a common good.
- d) These experiences are meant to enhance learning through service and they should not compromise academic rigor even if the engagement may get personal and affect objectivity.
- e) To make the experience a systematic learning process, these projects typically include a structured time for critical reflection from students and evaluation.

All the above implies that the civic mission of a university when acting through service learning, these initiatives imply changes in the mindset of those managing the educational processes and running the university regarding ordinary teaching and research activities.

According to Culum (2005) these factors explain why, when universities engage in civic actions they consider ways to integrate knowledge and experience in ways that directly benefit teachers and students; in other words, they seek to promote attitudinal changes among stakeholders to address the needs of the community while upholding the traditional role of the university. A responsible design of these activities typically considers the university's work, expertise and partnerships; its readiness to include alternatives models of educating and researching; and offering the students the support they need during the process of community-engaged learning.

In a similar way Peric (2012) asserts that when universities implement responsible activities, they give direction to educational processes and outcomes by enhancing civil participation, promoting the spread of mutual understanding about others' needs and potentials, and specifically in universities by encouraging youngsters to actively engage in activities that contribute toward more democratic and fair societies as students and future graduates.

This implies that the involvement of students through service learning programs creates a fertile context for experiential education, where reciprocal learning is fostered as both sides - those who provide service and those who received it- learn from experience.

Peric describes service learning as a *teaching method* that is integrated into the curricula and typically offers a frame for students to consider, discuss and analyze the learning experience while carrying out the activities set by the program seeking to contribute to the betterment of society and to develop a sense of caring for others.

He argues that different from traditional approaches to education, programs that work based on service learning *support students to experience a learning and growth opportunity through three steps* leading to a progression of the learning process. The model proposed by this author is based on three basic areas the students are invited to answer: what was done; what are the consequences and what are the future implications. In other words:

1. *What happened?* Here students make an initial and systematic observation of what they observe during the work done at the community. The connection between the goals and the activities carried out, the features of the partnership, the roles of each participant, including the student him/herself. What was shared and what could be learnt from that interaction.

2. *So what?* Students learn to value the relevance of activities in relation to study programs; how goals connect with each other to find solutions to problems, how students contribute from where they are best prepared and how they put their own values into practice. Students learn to value how the experience contributes to their personal and professional development and to connect problems to causes and ways to address and alleviate them.

3. *Now what?* Refers to how students are expected to use and extend their new knowledge in the future, their community involvement, but next time as students and professionals. In most cases students may also be expected to assess activities themselves looking at aspects that need to improve shall the program be continued or repeated.

A final observation that can be made about the literature analyzed about service learning is that most of the authors included coincide in that it constitutes a sustainable strategy through which universities accomplish their civic mission and materialize their extension activities.

This is so because service learning systematically integrates those projects and activities with the traditional roles of teaching and researching by implementing models that include community-engaged learning experiences in ways that combine *in practice* both roles.

Service learning represents a strategy that colligates the university's inherent roles with the needs of society as it creates channels through which universities offer more than a venue for academic formation and become platforms from where positive initiatives can be launched and directed; this means that they contribute to the formation of the students that will account with professional competences needed toward the insertion of graduates in the labor markets that will also become part of their societies as productive and responsible citizens.

Referring to the need universities feel in offering their students those competences, Fields (2011) analyses how *competency-based curriculum* is changing pedagogical strategies aiming to bring students to the center of the learning process through generating competencies by using a new kind of curricula. Where the major characteristic of this approach is that students need to show that they have acquired a set of theoretical knowledge that can be used and put in practice as actual skills in working places.

According to her as the education models are transforming and shifting from a traditional knowledge-based curriculum towards a more competency-based oriented curriculum, universities face now more than ever the need to re-structure not only what they teach but also how they teach it. These changes are being reported to bring new opportunities to students at the time of facing new job opportunities. She concludes in saying that:

"The Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC), as opposed to outcomes-based curriculum, focuses on accountability and curricular outcomes that promote student-centered learning. It also focuses on the application, not merely acquisition, of knowledge [...]. Since competency infers the highest level of what students should demonstrate, CBC suggests a framework whereby skill sets are mastered, with these skills integrated through numerous courses. Instructors work together to identify skill sets that are paramount in the workforce and then develop individualized class activities that address the skills. In this way, instructors provide opportunity for students to recognize how the skill set can be applied in numerous courses. Students internalize that the competency, not mere knowledge, is what will be most important in the workforce arena [...]."

5.2. Engaged research

In previous pages we have seen how the university commits to contributing to the betterment of society by providing channels and forms of education through which it aims at making

students aware of their potentials and the need to produce professionals that are equipped to carry their careers as sensitive citizens. In following pages we focus on the second role of the university (production of knowledge) and how the research it produces contributes to better understand and improve living conditions of communities outside campus.

When a university engages in research, by the very definition of what a university is, doing research is generally accepted as a socially beneficial activity because it is revising, conserving, updating or creating knowledge; and hence when that knowledge is useful for the community then the university is materializing its mission. Doing research is, as we have discussed, one of the roles of the university, however the point we rise here is *what kind of research* and *research for what purpose* should the university do so as to be socially responsible.

Modern societies require increasing volumes and quality of academic research; with its traditional creativity, diversity and objectivity to address the problems societies face universities stand in a crucial place to answer that call.

According to Whitmer et al. (2010) no other social actor is better prepared to do this more than universities and research institutions; they stand on a strategic point from where they produce and integrate answers to many social demands; universities gather information and understand communities due to their research capabilities and they too come up with original and effective solutions to some of those social problems.

However important challenges have historically remained in terms of the *translation* of those efforts and outcomes from the university's research to bring their academic outputs to be of use for the general public and to policy makers. In other words how research outcomes actually affect society.

The way research has historically been done has tended to detach the research process from any form of *subjective influence* from the environment to the research process and its outcomes; being the positivist paradigm of science the clearest example of how scholars have sought to separate research from the influence of social needs or subjective expectations.

This trend however is under deep revision and change; recent decades have shown increasing interest among scholars in turning university's research into a more sensitive, socially colligated and responsible process. This shift in research paradigms has brought about what has come to be known as *engaged research*.

McDonald (2006) describes this kind of research as *translational research* as it *translates* scientific discoveries into practical applications that improve community life, where the main goal of any investigative activities enable researchers to strengthen the connection between research and practice producing results that are applied to real life.

She defines community-engaged research as an approach used to conduct research -not a methodology- that utilizes qualitative and quantitative methods to produce knowledge; that recognizes and actually builds on the strengths of the community functioning as a partner. What characterizes community-engaged research is not the methods but the principles that lead the research and the way researchers and communities relate in a partnership based on cooperation and negotiation toward an agreed strategy to address issues a community faces.

She asserts that when a university carries out research that is engaged with the problems of a community it is committing itself to produce a double benefit -to itself and to the community- that is more direct and intertwined in terms of process and results; and where both inputs and outputs from the research are credited to all parties in the process. When research is done in correlation with outreach activities it usually takes the form of engaged research, which implies four key elements:

1. Inclusion of the views of the community in the definition of the research topic;
2. Community members are part of the solution to problems rather than passive receivers;
3. The research process develops in a frame of shared decision making between researchers and community members; and
4. Typically there is an agreed strategy for the dissemination of findings and their applicability.

Going beyond the issue of geographical vicinity, universities are engaging in growing number of projects that bring together communities and regions that would have been, if not impossible at least difficult, to connect and cooperate in the past. It is widely known that the development of communication means and technologies are rapidly changing this.

In this regard Madorrán-García (2012) focuses on the analysis of the challenges universities face when embarking on social responsible activities that relate to broader scenarios as they engage in projects of, for example, international solidarity and international cooperation towards development. According to this author, from a normative perspective universities are increasingly expected to make more contributions in the area of international cooperation for development by making social responsible research an inherent part of their missions and by making their research activities overcome traditional views that portray universities as *knowledge industries* or *professional factories*.

Clearly this is challenging the traditional ways in which universities have created and maintained knowledge into a more horizontal and balanced relation with society.

5.2.1. Features of engaged research

Following Whitmer et al. (2010) most research processes can be classified into a continuum of categories that described as *basic research*, *applied research*, *knowledge-to-action research* and *engaged research*. This last form represents one of the key ways in which science relates to society; hence the importance of the role of the university in this aspect when approaching its social roles and responsibilities.

Engaged research is characterized by the fact that research topics are defined with inputs from the community object of the research -not unilaterally by the researchers as it happens in the traditional paradigm-; an another important difference with traditional research is that this approach is based on conceptual models of social change; hence looking at ways to challenge undesirable situations, while producing quality and objective scientific knowledge.

Engaged research is typically framed within universities in their outreach and extension programs, cutting through academic activities, which implies producing, transmitting and using that knowledge to generate or direct social changes that benefit the academic and non-academic communities involved.

Fitzgerald (2006) includes among the features of the engaged research the following aspects:

1. Research is typically applied and has practical goals;
2. The community becomes more than just the object of the research to be a participant of the process of deciding goals, data and methods;
3. Due to the participation of different stakeholders this is a *contractual* kind of research;
4. It includes alternative ways of data gathering and share; and
5. It usually accounts with evaluation and assessment of outcomes that are inclusive of the opinion of community members.

The key concept in engaged research is *knowledge transfer* as knowledge is relevant in practical terms to the community affected; he asserts however, that this kind of research should be based on technical and scientific methods that may result in publications and presentations as forms of dissemination of findings, hence giving relevance to more traditional research paradigms.

As it can be seen, in engaged research the relation between the participants and researchers becomes more fluid, as the traditional role of the observers is more relative to that of the subject of the research. The traditional vertical approach shifts to a new strategy where the researcher interacts directly with the subject and where the subject has a say in what is to be researched, how and how the outcomes are to be used.

According to McDonald (2006) in community-engaged research this change represents a shift to a more horizontal relation where the subject (the community object of the investigation) becomes a participant that collaborates with the researcher by providing its views and knowledge; hence in this kind of research communities are empowered and have a say in the way knowledge is produced and utilized.

This author concludes that community-engaged research builds on the established methods of traditional research, however the difference lays in the nature of the relation between the participants (community and researchers) that now are called to cooperate as partners.

Although the kind and strength of the partnership varies from case to case, it is the idea of *working together* what validates the outcomes. By jointly defining the research problem, the approach to it and the ways partners will intervene to address it is what makes the difference with traditional research. In so doing community-engaged research includes the full spectrum of research involving the community as a collaborator.

The process of identifying the research problem can happen as a top-down approach when for instance researchers identify a problem and request community leaders to participate in finding the data to support their hypothesis and to develop practical solutions. Or it can also happen as a down-top process when community leaders ask researchers (typically at the university level) to assist them in systematically addressing matters of their concern. In both cases the synergy created helps the development of further steps such as finding and securing the necessary resources to carry the project forward and shortening the time gap between the moment of discovery and implementation of policies to address the issues of concern.

It is appreciated among scholars in this kind of research that community members provide to the researchers with insights that may be culturally sensitive, they help designing accurate measurement tools; community members also help understanding at the time of analyzing the data by infusing light in culturally related matters and the design of intervention strategies. They also contribute to the research process in carrying out and facilitating the evaluation the community does at the grass root level of the outcomes of the intervention.

Israel et al. (2001) go a step beyond in the analysis of engaged research to include and delineate the differences between the concepts of *community-based participatory research* as compared to *community-based research*. Where the first emphasizes the participation and control given to non-academic researchers in producing new knowledge and driving social change. According to these authors this kind of research process grants the community a social and cultural entity whose active engagement is not only expected but also deemed central to the outcomes of the process. While the second concept focuses on conducting research in a community as a place or setting, which becomes the object of the process, with limited contribution from community members to a researcher-driven endeavor.

These authors summarize key principles that characterize and guide community based research that is participatory in the following terms:

1. It acknowledges the community as a unit of identity;
2. It builds on strengths and resources of the community and the researchers;
3. It facilitates involvement of all partners in all phases of the research;
4. It integrates knowledge and action for the benefit of all partners;
5. It promotes co-learning and empowerment of all parties;
6. It involves a cyclical and interactive process;
7. It addresses the research topic from both positive and ecological perspectives;
8. It disseminates findings and knowledge gained to all partners; and
9. It involves a long-term commitment by all partners.

Similarly Janke & Shelton (2011, p.6) describe *community-engaged research* as a creative activity that, through collaboration generates, refines, conserves and shares knowledge in a way that is mutually beneficial.

"[...] knowledge is generated in collaboration with, communicated to, and validated by peers in academe and the community. Community-engaged research and creative activity produces products informed by (multi-disciplinary knowledge, including but not limited to publications, exhibitions, and programs that simultaneously meets campus mission and goals as well as addresses issues of societal concern. It is research or creative activities that involve systematic inquiry, produces results that are publicly observable, allows for critique and is available for other to use and develop. Community-engaged research and creative activities demonstrate methodological rigor through the use of methods that are appropriate to the goals, questions, and context of the work."

Sandmann (n.d.) agrees to the above and contributes to the debate in saying that Community-engaged scholarship is heterogeneous, multidirectional, collaborative, highly participatory, and serves multiple audiences. In general, this kind of research has structural similarities with traditional research, however, because it involves the community in the process, it is based on a different epistemological base that offers a wider set of values and goals.

An important difference that is typically seen in research that engages the community is the way findings from the research are used, while in traditional research data found will normally be used for academic publications as research papers that may eventually contribute to support and produce policy changes; in engaged and participatory research findings are shared between all stakeholders in terms of how those findings will be disseminated and utilized. Hence, while researchers will work toward academic publications, community leaders will normally pursue rather practical ways to make that information available to the general public and to policymakers, therefore making use of other channels such as meetings, radio or TV programs, newspapers, conferences or workshops that are more easily available to the general audience and that may have a bigger impact in the decisions of those in charge of setting policies and strategies to address the issues of concern.

Challenges may arise as a different sense of timing typically exist among community members and those involved in academic research; while for scholars outcomes from research may need time for maturation and further scientific validation toward publication; on the other side, those in the community level may be more interested in solving the problems as soon as possible, which in some cases may relate to political and personal agendas.

Whitmer et al. (2010) refer to this process in terms of the *disciplinary issues* and the *role of the peer review*, which they define as the process happening before a scientific publication

takes place and as the professional assessment of faculty for the promotion within academia. As a whole the peer review process seeks to ensure that any scientific work is well vetted, however it can be not only painful for the researchers but very time consuming delaying the applicability of the outcomes from the research in the real world some times for years or even decades. This delay in the transfer of academic knowledge to society is an aspect that engaged research seeks to address and the increasing use of multidisciplinary approaches together with the notion of multi-author research papers seem to bring a pragmatic solution.

Likewise academic issues might arise from more conservative researchers as engaged research may appear less rigorous, less objective, politically biased, lacking a firm theoretical ground and not necessarily generalizable, hence rendering it less scientific and less valuable by researchers that do not use this approach.

5.2.2. Partners in research

In engaged research too, universities interact with other parties and form partnerships to produce mutual benefits; these relations include stakeholders like public agencies or private organizations; usual examples of community partners are health or education ministries, local community groups like schools, churches or other religious groups, NGOs of all sorts, organizations that bring together ethnic or minority groups, etc.

Among the many examples of stakeholders that can be observed in these initiatives we can identify the individuals (be them the researchers or the community members); groups of families that benefit from a particular project, agencies like public or non-government organizations that participate as partners, the people involved in the delivery of the project and the community as a whole.

An important issue here is to consider what glues them together, what are the aspects that make such a variety of stakeholders come together and wish to cooperate. Fitzgerald (2006) explains that these partnerships usually work because they are based on shared ideas and principles, because stakeholders have a common vision of what they do, why they do it and what goals they expect to achieve from what they do.

This explains why engaged research projects are typically built on relations based on mutual trust and cooperation where information and responsibilities are shared transparently and seek to bring benefits for all participants, enhancing the capacity of the communities towards self-sufficiency while promoting scholarly development among those in the university.

McDonald (2006) identifies the general areas in which partners contribute, in this author's views researchers help in academically framing the topics and approach, for instance in defining questions and methodology, networking capabilities that may contribute to financing of projects, and providing legitimacy based on its own traditional mission; while community members provide personnel and advice on logistics, developing the contribution from alternative grass-root level networks, advice on how to tailor the context.

5.2.3. Goals and outcomes

According to Fitzgerald (2006) engaged research happens when universities set themselves to enrich their scholarly production, promote their creative activities, enhance learning and curricular development; prepare educated and engaged researchers and citizens, strengthen democratic values and civic responsibility and contribute to the common good.

He sees that engaged research produces initial, intermediate and long term outcomes that typically affect in a positive way all the stakeholders involved in the projects by producing

changes in the attitudes, developing skills, values and more committed behaviors, while also bringing positive changes in the norms and relationships among individuals and institutions.

Among the goals of carrying out community-engaged research there is the need to shorten the period connecting discoveries from research and applicability of the discoveries in everyday life. McDonald (2006) explains that in research carried out in health services, for example, it may take 10 to 25 years between the moment in which research advancements are produced and the moment those discoveries are put in practice. This happens because communication channels between researchers and community leaders may be poor or even non-existent; which creates gaps and hindrances in terms of benefits that could be obtained in a much timely manner if that research had been done in more cooperative ways.

By using a community-engaged approach research may better connect shorter and longer term goals and function as what the author calls *translational research*, which means setting alternative priorities based on the link between research and practice by improving communication and implementation channels.

The active participation of community in the process helps developing ownership among community members that contribute to the continuation and sustainability of these programs given that they directly participate in defining interventions to be done and help evaluating outcomes as they can collect data from community response to those interventions. In the words of McDonald (2006) *community involvements helps ensuring recruitment and retention of personnel for the project as well as community buy-in.*

Whitmer et al. (2010) assert that evidence suggests that knowledge created through this research is more effective in achieving practical solutions intended to address because through the process of involving the communities researchers open the channels for more social acceptance of the interventions proposed, normally are policy relevant and account with positive impacts and expectations. These authors conclude this idea in saying (p. 314):

“Interaction between scientist and members of the local communities (ie community or societal engagement) is integral to engaged research but is not limited solely to communicating scientific findings. Rather, community engagement includes a diverse palette of techniques in 1) education, both formal and informal; 2) consultation in policy, practice, and planning; and 3) training the next generation of scientists, decision makers, and citizens.”

Sandmann (n.d., p.3) describes it as a kind of research that promotes a kind of *“hands-on interdisciplinary approach most conducive to innovation [...] that adds chairs to the research table, bringing new perspectives to research and topics.”*

All of which clearly contributes toward the democratization of the production and access to knowledge, making the effort of producing responsible research more feasible and efficient.

5.2.4. Final observations on engaged research

In the previous pages we have analyzed the problem of how to connect research as one or the traditional roles of the university to the community in a cooperative way that contributes to responsible and beneficial kinds of research.

Cooper (n.d.) describes the notion of engaged research by calling it *use-inspired-research by the university* meaning that it constitutes a mechanism born out of the university aimed to enhancing socio-economic developments for a community, this also implies that universities have a central role in producing and mapping knowledge as a form of social responsiveness and production of social capital.

Community engagement and participatory research offer a broad spectrum of cooperation for universities and communities, as mentioned it can greatly contribute to better defining research processes and to enhance reliability and validity of new knowledge, it can broaden both formal and informal channels of communication between universities and their communities; however risks and challenges may arise and remain for example in terms of securing the veracity and scientific consistency of research processes and outcomes; securing a proper distribution of tasks, responsibilities and credits among partners; keeping control of budgetary management and the transparency in the decision making processes; etc.

While it is a positive idea to engage different stakeholders in the research process as they can contribute to enriching research perspectives, methods and measurement of variables and they can help researchers make better informed decisions; it is also true that involvement must be meaningful in all aspects of the projects, and this refers to the benefits engaged research will produce to all parts. Outcomes from the process must remain transferable and usable for all partners so as to ensure future cooperation in the same or different projects.

5.3. Social responsibility and university extension and outreach

“Scholarship is about creating, synthesizing, and applying knowledge to address the issues important in our world. Scholarship is also about respecting and learning from the knowledge and wisdom of others, our colleagues and the citizens with whom we work. Extension educators are full and essential players in the scholarly process of knowledge creation, synthesis, and application.” Alter (2003)

5.3.1. Extension and outreach

To understand what social responsibility of the university means we need to explore the work universities do as *extension and outreach*; activities falling into these categories constitute yet another communication channel, a different arena for interaction between the academic world and the communities where universities work and exist.

University extension and outreach shares with the previous roles (teaching and researching) the goal of bringing positive changes to society, however not necessarily through academic work or methods. This *alternative role* strengthens the social relevance of the university with activities carried out the people therein at times as organized academic bodies or as inorganic and rather spontaneous groups of students, professors or staff that get together for example as volunteers that join their energies to offer services or assistance to communities in need.

According to Lasley (2008) extension and outreach describe the efforts that link the university, its faculties, personnel and students with local citizens and communities in addressing high priority issues and problems of those communities. These activities may or may not be integrated in the formal programs of the universities and are characterized as activities where academic peers and lay leaders provide inputs, support and assistance helping identify and address social problems and to design ways of intervention that may or may not relate to formal educational programs.

Some authors understand extension and outreach as a *window* that connects the efforts carried out by the academic community as *cooperative efforts* through which communities in general, their citizens, governments, other agencies and businesses can have access to research-generated knowledge and obtain assistance to address some of the socioeconomic issues that affect them.

The University of Rhode Island, for example, in its website refers to its *Cooperative Extension* in the following words:

"It is our belief that well-informed citizens possess the ability to solve environmental, economic and social challenges of our state and world. Our value of lifelong learning, community engagement and protecting the natural environment is reflected in all of the Center's programs and services." (<http://www.uri.edu/cels/ceoc/> retrieved on June 10th 2013)

While in a similar way the Extension and Outreach Department of the university of Virginia Tech describes this *other mission* by saying that it means *"extending [the university's] resources in order to address public needs through non-formal, non-credit educational programs"*. (http://www.hnfe.vt.edu/extension_and_outreach/index.html retrieved on June 15th 2013)

From a broader perspective Tünnermann Bernheim (2000) explains that throughout history universities have progressively taken more proactive roles as promoters of social change by implementing programs that allow them to extend their work and to reach out to society by disseminating and applying the knowledge they have and produce. According to this author the increasing institutionalization of extension and outreach demonstrates the will of universities to promote democratic participation and a civic sense among students and professionals in addressing everyday problems in their communities.

Through the review carried for this study it was noticed that *Extension* and *Outreach* activities are frequently referred to as *the third role of the university*, because different from teaching and researching, extension and outreach describe a kind of *alternative work* or form of interaction that is not necessarily academic.

Extension and *outreach* are typically understood as the efforts done within the framework of the university aimed at bringing together its potentials and use some of its resources jointly in ways that benefit communities outside campus. In the literature these concepts were also found as *cooperative extension*, which implies that activities are recognized as integral part of the university's engagement outside campus.

Although in most cases *extension* and *outreach* are used as synonyms and exchangeable terms in practice -by the universities when they describe what they do in this area- and in theory -by those researchers analyzing the phenomenon-; in truth, although related and sometimes overlapping, they mean and represent different things. In the following pages the reader should notice that not all *extension* activities are *outreach* and the same, not all *outreach* activities are *extension*.

The difference lays in that on the one hand *extension* refers to those activities universities implement where they *prolong* what they do; this implies that already existing programs or activities are *extended* or *expanded* to other realms to include other stakeholders or to allow for more flexibility to different audiences, for instance in terms of access in time and form to ongoing programs to more people. A university providing free and open courses on some skill development or distance and online courses represent examples of extension. They are *teaching* outside their own academic community.

Here extension allows wider access to knowledge for broader audiences (for example be them enrolled students or not) to courses, this represents a way in which a university expands its ongoing activities (teaching) to other areas or communities. Extension also refers to other forms of teaching and learning such as online educational services, distance or short courses like summer sessions and the like where the university offers alternative ways of education

for people wishing to participate of those courses even if they are not necessarily enrolled as students and courses do not yield credits.

Extension also refers to students' welfare and access to affordable health care systems, it may include services like housing and access to information on scholarships or loans, work opportunities, and other kind of information. It may also refer to social circles and activities organized within the university for the students and the staff including sports or other recreational activities.

On the other hand the concept of outreach generally implies activities where the university carries out projects or activities that are not necessarily based on existing academic programs nor that necessarily include educational work. Examples of this include the formation of groups of volunteers to help communities in a wide range of ways that are not directly related to the accomplishment of academic outcomes. Activities of this sort may relate closer to charity and social assistance; outreach activities are usually described more in terms of aiding and supporting vulnerable communities rather than educationally oriented.

Lasley (2008) explains the difference between *extension* and *outreach* by providing examples of activities carried out by university departments or faculties that constitute engaged outreach but not extension. These initiatives can for instance be taken by associations of students independently from their studies, they can be implemented in programs of distance education, they can happen in areas of external relations of the university with governments or other organizations or agents, it can also happen as faculty members being quoted in the media, or when academics are interviewed for their expertise and serve as consultants; all these examples represent instances of outreach that however are not extension.

As mentioned, in the great majority of the literature analyzed the two concepts (extension and outreach) are presented as exchangeable synonyms and only for the sake of simplicity we will keep them as such in the upcoming pages, however the reader should be aware of the above basic conceptual differences.

5.3.2. Goals of extension and outreach programs

When universities design and implement extension and outreach activities and especially when they include those initiatives as integral part of the institutions' mission and vision, what they are doing is putting the potentials the universities have to work in the search of solutions to practical problems as well as expanding their influence as agents of change in the societies where they work by committing to go beyond their traditional roles.

Extension and outreach typically play a key role in the universities' translational mission; that is to say in bridging education institutions with social needs by *putting knowledge to work* and allowing academics, staff and students to easily reach out to the communities and help them disseminate and use what they know and the outcomes from the research they do, while they also are given the opportunity to put that knowledge into practice.

These programs are widely believed to create safety networks and spaces for people, especially for youth at risk, as they participate in activities that make them feel useful and help keeping them in school, so in many cases universities set these programs seeking to support and promote internal and external safety nets.

As mentioned, universities account with important resources that exceed financial and economic means, like their human capabilities, accumulated knowledge and capacity to produce new knowledge, prestige and authority, networking potentials, among many others.

Extension and outreach initiatives represent a *third channel* universities have to create opportunities for synergy in the search for social solutions and development.

In many cases universities set these activities to create spaces for the students to have opportunities to get real world experience; this means that faculties or departments support students to design, develop and deliver social services to communities outside campus while doing research in the areas where they study and where they seek to develop their expertise.

Just to provide an example the College of Agriculture and Life Sciences (CAL S) at Cornell University in its website states that a key principle of the College's mission is to:

"put experience and research to work in order to serve the public good and make a positive impact around the globe. This "knowledge with a public purpose" encourages lifelong learning by reaching out locally, nationally, and internationally with programs that broadly benefit the public, rural and urban communities, and industry. [...] CAL S' outreach and extension efforts build community capacity, protect the environment, influence the decision-making processes of myriad stakeholders (e.g., families, businesses, governments), and improve lives by enhancing the economic well-being of people and communities." (Retrieved on 10th June 2013 from <http://cals.cornell.edu/outreach-extension>)

When analyzing the goals universities seek to achieve by implementing these initiatives, a key aspect to consider is the setting of groups of volunteers typically to serve communities outside campus. The motivations behind these initiatives provide good example of how universities make good use of the *alternative* resources they have.

As mentioned in the review in chapter 2 Wolford, Cox, & Culp (2001) researched on the role that volunteer groups have in the extension and outreach programs of universities and among their findings they assert that throughout history university extension has taken place as the institutions sought to expand their educational influence and to generate broader impacts to wider audiences through the use of volunteers. Citing Laughlin (1990) these authors focus on educational aspects of extension and outreach and explain that volunteers provide diversity of extension contacts to targeted groups who might not be reached by other methods.

According to these authors volunteers increase the depth and continuity of university's extension and outreach programs by allowing professionals to teach other subject matters of a more *advanced* nature in that they can go across the walls of the classroom into real life situations. While at the same time volunteers have an opportunity to interact with other students and volunteers and gain skills and information from those interactions, some related to their academic endeavors and others of a more personal nature.

These authors argue that as students engage in volunteer activities they gain self-satisfaction and expand knowledge and skills as they are emotionally attached to goals and procedures of the activities. And to top it all these activities produce an obvious benefit in that volunteers support and foster other contributions to the social tissue as they promote and deepen the knowledge base of individuals at homes, businesses, and the community at large.

Of relevance for this study on social responsibility of the university is the fact that these authors analyzed in their research the factors that motivate volunteers to engage. If we consider that being responsible means managing the impacts of decisions and actions, clearly the social role these groups have, the reasons why they are formed and how they function are important aspects universities cannot leave outside their consideration.

Wolford, Cox, & Culp found that there are various kinds of motivations that basically relate to volunteers' personal achievements; their affiliation to a group; and the ways in which they relate to other as in relations of power.

Their research found that when volunteers join motivated by personal achievements they do it based on the will to learn new things; the desire to contribute to their community; the wish of making good use of their leisure time; the search for formal and informal recognition; and the expectation that working as volunteers will lead to employment opportunities.

Regarding volunteers that join these groups seeking to have a sense of belonging usually do it based on the idea that extension activities are good for the organization; because they seek to meet other volunteers and interact with them; some volunteer because their families encourage them or because they have friends that are involved; and lastly some join these groups because they perceive that more people like them and accept them if they join in.

Lastly these authors found that there are people who join volunteer groups as a consequence of the relations of power the groups generate, as such some volunteers recognize motivating elements like the chance and space to do things they like; they see opportunity for leadership; others feel they are responsible for volunteer programs and the continuation of the services they provide; and some others join because they feel they receive some form of status.

Understanding these aspects is a key element for those universities and professors wishing to make their institutions and programs socially engaged and more responsible because by understanding the reasons why people (particularly students) wish to volunteer they can create more synergic plans that combine the resources available within the universities with the energies and the motivations people have and hold dear.

5.3.3. Extension and outreach in action

Although over time extension and outreach have changed and adapted to new social demands and available resources, these activities continue to address a wide range of aspects that in general involve issues like human wellbeing, security, economic, social and cultural development, as well as environmental protection among many other areas.

Apel et al. (2013) explain that the nature and scope of the extension and outreach projects that universities design and implement are very varied because they can be born out of the communities themselves as they ask the university for help or guidance; or projects can also result from the initiative of students, professors or other staff in the universities who see possible areas where they can contribute to the betterment of certain social problems as palliatives or by addressing the root cause of some problems.

In most cases the life of the projects starts when they are designed and approved by relevant agents and then project managers recruit students and give priority to students from the communities in which the projects are implemented. The way in which this creational process happens greatly contributes to the heterogeneity of extension and outreach activities.

Likewise extension and outreach vary in nature and scope depending on the social needs they address; and as higher education institutions themselves constitute a very heterogeneous group, where resources, areas of interest and expertise, personnel available, geographic access among many other factors determine the ratio of action of these activities. Yet and expectably activities of this sort do share features, among which a major common element is that when extension and outreach are implemented as part of an institutional plan of the university they make expertise meet public needs.

Among the areas that more typically universities describe in their websites this study found that the following are the most frequently mentioned topics where universities promote their extension and outreach activities:

- Development and spread of existing academic and educational programs in different formats and for different audiences, for example in long distance or online courses.
- Promotion of cultural activities that foster access to arts, engaging society, both as an active producer of culture and as a passive observer.
- Dissemination of access to knowledge for example by promoting access and use of libraries and online academic services with communities outside academia.
- Support small and medium size business as many of these activities help individuals learn new ways to produce income through alternative enterprises, improved marketing strategies, and management skills than help them improve productivity.
- Assist vulnerable communities of different kinds in their basic needs.
- Etc.

Just to provide a few out of the many possible examples the New Carolina State University in its extension and outreach webpage explains the strategy it follows in order to:

“ [...] enrich lives and drive economic good for the people of the state based on its long tradition of developing solutions for real-world problems that address issues that cover from food safety to helping businesses stay competitive, while its extension and outreach programs are aimed at helping people in remote communities to improve their quality of life”. (<http://www.ncsu.edu/outreach/extension/> retrieved on 13th June 2013)

To reach those goals the university offers two programs, the *North Carolina Cooperative Extension Service* and the *Industrial Extension Service* both of which focus on four areas: 1. Enhancing agricultural, forest and food systems; 2. Developing responsible youth; 3. Strengthening and sustaining families; and 4. Conserving and improving the environment and natural resources.

According to the university through educational programs, publications and events, its cooperative extension delivers research-based information to local citizens to offer them practical solutions that include a variety of issues that go from controlling household insects, to protecting well water, to helping families improve eating habits, to improving indoor air quality; hence demonstrating the broad nature of its extension programs.

An other example can be found in the University of Missouri for instance, which according to the information provided in its extension and outreach website, the university accounts with projects involving students and academic personnel working on the areas of agriculture, natural resources, lawn and garden, home and consumer life, nutrition and health, families and relationships, community and leadership, business and careers, and emergency management. (Retrieved on June 8th 2013 from <http://extension.missouri.edu/index.aspx>)

University of Campinas provides yet another example, as an essential element of extension and outreach initiatives is that they directly contribute to the university's pedagogical and social mission because they bring the institution closer to the community it aims to serve. The same as many others, the university has a special office that is responsible for receiving and stimulating proposals that include joint efforts of technical, administrative and operational staff using the institution's funds or funds obtained from partnerships with other institutions, public bodies, non-governmental organizations or public or private companies to bring the university more in touch with the problems and needs of the surrounding communities.

The initiatives include programs, events, publications, technological, educational, cultural and social products and the provision of services, to promote the development of physical, cultural and social well-being, foster democratic values, equal rights, participation and to ensure respect for the individual and for sustainable environmental actions.

Extension and outreach activities in University of Campinas promote the spread of popular culture; the history and memory of social movements; restoration of citizenship to street dwellers and indigenous people; social inclusion of individuals with special physical needs; socio-environmental education; sustainable agriculture; socially responsible economics; and the appreciation of culture as a tool for promoting health and well-being.

Through these activities the university as a whole strives to make itself an agent of knowledge that contributes to the development of policies that reduce social exclusion, promote responsible citizenship, help address key social problems and pave the way to accomplish some social aspirations. (Retrieved on June 15th 2013, University's Vice-President message João Frederico Meyer <http://www.unicamp.br/unicamp/content/2013/01/04/extension-and-outreach?language=en>)

From a more academic perspective Apel et al. (2013) describe extension and outreach of the universities in the context of *externships* as a form of extension and outreach saying that:

"Community sustainability projects are multi-disciplinary activities involving individuals, community organizations, externs, Extension faculty, and campus resources. They foster the enhancement of social and natural resources, address community needs, and contribute to community resilience. The program integrates multiple perspectives into Extension programs on sustainable living, including the ways that choices, decisions, and behaviors affect natural resources, equity, and economic development at the local, regional, national, and global scales."

These authors focus their analysis on the disciplines of medicine, nursing, and law and mark the difference with interns and externs, where the first group are typically defined as unpaid students who cooperate with professionals for short-term periods; although both cases seek to expose students to the day-to-day matters of their careers, in the case of externships create opportunities for students to gain experience by interacting and participating in community engagement programs which according to the authors leads to create a much higher ownership of the experience and responsibility.

From a different perspective we also consider recent trends in extension and outreach as they relate to the role of new technologies and communication tools. These developments have completely re-shuffled the ways in which universities interact with society and spread their programs to audiences that may be even on the other side of the planet. This in turn brings promising opportunities in expanding the frontiers universities reach, but also challenges by disconnecting communities that find it difficult or impossible to access new technologies.

Authors like DeYoung, Harris, & Larsen (1995), for example, have analyzed how the lack of computers, equipment and communication technologies related equipment and/or skills can disconnect rural clientele from enriching collaboration or information exchanges with universities, agencies and other sources, which is a key factor universities should consider if they aim at reaching those in more need through extension and outreach.

New technologies are bringing the benefits of extension and outreach to areas and audiences that had previously been considered impossible. The examples of this kind of extension and outreach are multiple and growing everyday as more people and areas of the world get access to communication technologies. These new ways of interaction provide original insights and always growing alternatives of interaction between universities and communities, which is producing great impacts on the ways, universities deliver more amount and different kinds of extension and outreach programs.

DeYoung, Harris, & Larsen (1995) describe this phenomenon in saying:

"A virtual community is a collection of people with mutual interests, communicating through linkages provided by networked computers. Networked computers tied into the Internet, an international web of computers linking more than 20 million users, are often characterized as the "highways of the mind." These communication networks are formed by the integration of computers, telecommunications systems, and database technology [...]. This powerful convergence of technology enables network users to interact with each other and quickly retrieve diverse sources of information."

Clearly, increased connectivity generates new spaces for more synergy where universities can get to know more about the communities and vice versa and mutually create new ways of cooperation and interaction all of which takes us back to the need universities face in terms of being responsible actors and managing the social impacts of the actions they carry out.

5.3.4. Systematization of extension and outreach

The level of systematization of extension and outreach activities is indeed wide and offers ample space for activities to fall into many categories. Through this study we found initiatives that take place as inorganic and spontaneous projects taken for example by students doing volunteer activities seeking to bring about positive changes in a given community. While at a more structural and organic level, sometimes professors or departments of a university carry out activities of this sort and they account with institutional support from the university. This may include for example using the name of the university to gain access to a community, to obtain authority and legitimacy based on the *brand* that the university represents and facilitating the process of fund rising for the activities.

At a higher level of organization, extension and outreach initiatives may grow to include whole departments or faculties and become stable programs -not just sporadic ones-. In this case the university typically recognizes the activities carried out by the people in a given department as part of their integral mission and provide a more institutional support and space for them. In many cases these programs will be considered as a structural part of the system and will account with allocations of budget from the university and represent noticeable elements of the universities' strategic plans.

Some times initiatives of this sort and awareness on their contributions continue to grow and expand to include in the decision making and implementation process actors outside the academic community; they become more interdisciplinary in nature, broader in scope and open to participation leading to new forms of institutionalization that link the university with other organizations through mechanisms like memorandums of understanding with more explicit distribution of responsibilities, tasks and engagement.

As extension and outreach continue to develop local and national governments have grown to see the potentials these activities bring to benefit broader communities and have, as a consequence, sought to boost those programs and even become part of the game.

More governments are creating and developing strategies to foster and enhance the active participation of universities with their social issues through extension and outreach. The literature shows growing interest on the part of the governments to continue to support universities to carry out extension and outreach in terms of providing funds, legal support and fostering networking and dialogue. An indicator of this is the fact that more governments at all levels and in all regions of the world are incorporating the universities as key actors contributing to the development of their strategic plans for cities, states, nations and even regional integration processes.

At a broader level a number of international organizations have set plans to further promote the systematic implementation of extension and outreach at the inter-university level; examples of this are the already mentioned work carried out based on the *Talloires Declaration* or by organizations like the Kellogg Commission or the Carnegie Foundation through its award on community engagement in the context of American universities.

While on a more academically oriented position organizations like the *Journal of Extension* (JOE: <http://www.joe.org/>) create spaces and opportunities for professionals and students researching on extension and outreach to expand and promote initiatives and knowledge by publishing research and creative work in the area to encourage professional development and advancements in the theory and practice of the universities. JOE is an academic journal, working as a peer-reviewed paper that connects research on university outreach and engagement to educators and practitioners around the world.

Lastly it is worth mentioning that at the international level universities have shown an increasing level of awareness of the impact they have through their extension and outreach activities to the point that international conferences and extensive publications on the issue are taking place around the planet, bringing together universities from different countries and regions to get to know about each other's work and to develop new ways for partnership and strategies through which universities can design and deliver more services to communities well beyond their academic realm.

5.3.5. Extension and outreach in university's strategic plans

The growing awareness of the impact extension and outreach produce has led to growing number of university managers to incorporate in the strategic plans of the institutions' goals, procedures, financial and human resources and evaluation methods to initiatives of this sort.

The literature suggests that when extension and outreach are taken as an integral part of a university's mission leading to new social engagements, in a growing number of cases this is typically carried as an institutional effort that materializes through documenting the process and including them into university strategic plans in order to make them more accountable and better integrated into the activities and reporting system of the university.

Extension and outreach activities are being increasingly considered in the universities' regulations and may even be included among the areas that require special funding and resources. A quick browsing on the Internet on the existence of extension and outreach departments and offices among universities around the world greatly confirms this.

When these activities are set as structural elements of the university they produce behavioral changes and develop certain skills hence contributing to more responsible and self-aware universities. Archer et al. (2007) summarize this idea in saying that extension and outreach normally work on four goals or areas: developing knowledge, modifying attitudes, developing new skills and aspirations among participants and producing behavioral change that are considered positive and desirable and that spill over into the general social tissue.

When extension and outreach are included in the institutional strategic plan this evidences a particular kind of commitment from the university towards the communities and the desire to build new bridges and forms of interaction from within. Which in turn reflects the level of engagement from university authorities to those activities as they serve as a framework that guides the universities decision-making and setting of priorities to achieve their missions.

If universities make extension and outreach structural elements of the institution they typically seek to relate to their inner communities with actions that are well planned aiming

to generate the biggest possible positive impacts (that may or may not include academic outcomes) while reducing the waste of resources and preventing negative effects in order to better serve the targeted communities. In the cases where universities do account with strategic plans that include extension and outreach among their constituent elements, they typically include goals like:

1. Enhancing the delivery of traditional and alternative forms of extension and outreach programs and to act in such ways that universities are open and remain responsive before the changes that societies go through.
2. Influencing and designing ways to ensure enough funding for those initiatives from a number of different stakeholders in seeking to ensure sustainability of the projects.
3. Increasing the capacities of the university in all related departments and programs, while seeking to improve the quality of programs by engaging students to enhance their success and educational experience.
4. Seeking to increase universities' visibility and value before the communities they work with at local, national and international levels.

According to Auburn University's strategic plan for example, the university views its extension, outreach and continuing education activities as forms of engagement that provide value-added services to local communities while they *extend* the university's visibility to government and non government agencies, corporations, major foundations, which in turn helps the university in its fundraising efforts to finance those initiatives.

The document asserts: "*Well-executed outreach and continuing education can greatly expand our impact as an institution*", demonstrating both the interest of the managers on boosting the university's potentials in this regard and their commitment toward social change through the synergies the university can create. (Retrieved on June 13th 2013 from http://www.auburn.edu/communications_marketing/strategic_plan/p3i1.html)

In order to help universities' administrators, extension personnel and other leaders in their strive for improvement of the extension and outreach services they provide, Archer et al. (2007) developed a system to guide them to *define and measure excellence in extension and outreach* based on a set of descriptors that help them share and compare information with university administrators, potential funders, legislators, and the media.

These descriptors refer to the *uniqueness* of each project based on factors like how a project linkages the university to other communities; how it fosters participation and grassroots involvement from external communities; how projects are ensured in funding and setting partnership of local, state, regional, and federal entities; how these activities are designed and organized on research-based visions of the community; how programs promote lifelong learning; and how it empowers people involved through education and community-based problem solving strategies.

While the descriptors he proposes to describe *excellence* of extension and outreach refer to how projects anticipate and respond to critical issues; how they establish partnerships and engage with audiences, implement and evaluate activities; how to use partners' expertise to produce changes; understand economic, social, and environmental impacts programs have; and understand how the use of volunteers enhance and extend education.

According to this author, effective university managers find ways to ensure excellence in their programs and relations because they view them as an integral part of the university; which allows them to 1. give value to the variety of stakeholders involved as elements that shape the programs; 2. create the space for audiences receiving the services to express their views as a way to evaluate and re-shape programs; 3. account with ways to make the programs

easily identified and valued by those participating and benefiting; 4. understand and value the fact that these programs result in changes in people and institutions, hence the importance of guiding those changes in positive ways; 6. Considering economic impacts derived from their implementation; and 7. Ensuring necessary funding.

In their aim to boost meaningful extension and outreach, based on scientific measurement of excellence of the programs the authors created a matrix that combines specific data from each project with quality indicators that allow designers and practitioners to assess possible outcomes from any initiative a university wishes to take as extension and outreach.

The matrix works on two frameworks that combine the traditional academic perspective of universities on the one hand (referring to teaching and learning; discovery and scholarship; engagement; and management). While on the other it presents and analyzes information on extension and outreach specifically (including issues like university commitment; relevance of programs; quality of programs; outcomes and impacts; funding and external support).

According to these authors any university wishing to assess the extension and outreach work it does, can do it by inputting its own data into the boxes that allow them to identify criteria for excellence in their extension efforts.

5.3.6. The flip side of extension and outreach

In general terms there is agreement in that besides confronting students to real life experiences where they can learn to use their skills for the benefit of broader communities, extension and outreach also have important potentials to bring about positive effects as they colligate valuable resources in a way that makes the outputs of the projects typically be outstandingly effective in terms of costs and effects.

As we have seen in previous pages an important part of the literature analyzed for this section refers to the effects that extension and outreach activities of the universities have on their inner academic communities as well as on communities off campus. While there seems to be wide consensus on the fact that universities have great potentials to contribute to the betterment of society and to contribute to its advancements, there are also those who see that not all that glitters is gold and that call for more critical and realistic views of the effects university engagement can generate.

When universities set themselves into planning and implementing activities of extension and outreach they also need to have a clear vision of the impacts those initiatives may have in the communities both positive and negatively, in the present and well into the future.

Examples of negative effects include among others rendering the receiving communities even more vulnerable as they become more dependent on the services provided by the university or its personnel, hence making other stakeholders more reliant on university's support and allowing communities to divert necessary funds and resources to other areas or priorities.

University extension and outreach activities may also have negative effects when projects that are structured and planned for long run are suddenly discontinued, leaving the receiving community suddenly unattended. This may happen for example as financial resources dry off in the university, as volunteers lose motivation, or due to differences in goals and procedures of the programs among those leading the projects.

Communication problems may emerge at anytime between the different communities interacting in these projects leading to misunderstandings and some times disruption of programs that have been active for years or even decades. The same can be said about activities that do not account with transparent mechanisms to ensure transparency and

accountability or where projects do not account with clear procedures to distribute tasks, responsibilities and accomplishments.

Some times extension and outreach may be too focalized on one receiving community leaving other similar communities out of the project, generating unnecessary sensitiveness among communities and the university. The feeling of *why not us?* may arise among communities that see other communities receiving attention from a group of volunteers from a university while they are left aside rendering positive projects vulnerable to negligence or even sabotage by those feeling out casted.

Volunteer activities may also generate resentment among communities receiving the services if they perceive the volunteers or the universities as paternalistic and self-centered when they remain too close in their views, goals and procedures.

As mentioned in the review and to provide one representative example Stephenson (2003) worked on the effects that that extension and outreach produced among American farmers that had sought to be innovative by using new technologies. In this research the author showed that while universities -based on the predictions of a frame called *Innovation diffusion theory*- had assumed that new technologies emerging for the improvement of agricultural production would increase and favor more farmers, in truth after 30 years of working on this assumption and providing easy access to new technologies universities actually found they had favored big agricultural corporations that were more efficient in terms of accessing and using those technologies, which eventually pushed aside and out of the market to less competitive and smaller farmers that were their original targeted beneficiaries.

This study sets a clear example of how innovation and development of new technologies and creating more channels for access to it may in fact leave the target community in worse conditions than if the intervention from the university had not happened. Stephenson's study sets a striking example of how even if well-intentioned university extension and outreach may indeed affect negatively those it aims to serve.

All of the above serve as parameters at the time of setting extension and outreach activities and programs giving a key role to the need of evaluating the projects in all possible ways, considering side and long term effects to both the academic and non academic communities, this leads us once again to the need of the university to act and think responsibly, which means much more than just wanting to support a given community.

No extension or outreach project can by itself be based on the assumption that its impact will be positive and for good. The speculated benefits from it must also include careful attention to how the impacts of the project spread to other communities and over time. There is clearly the matter of fairness and equality to those aimed to receive the service, the issue of being open to change and adaptation to new conditions and audiences and avoiding biases.

5.3.7. Last observations on extension and outreach

Extension and outreach initiatives contain two major elements of the way universities interact with society: one, they allow for creative and interdisciplinary approaches through which a university relates with the world outside; and two, these aspects allow universities to play a more central role in the life of their societies as they become better integrated with them and they can explore new ways of creating synergy and producing new responses to the needs of their communities, countries and people.

Extension and outreach allow for spaces of direct communication that may be more informal and hence allow for more understanding and ways of evaluating and reforming interaction towards more effective ways to address social concerns.

We recall Tünnermann Bernheim (2000) in saying that higher education in the 21st century needs to develop on strategic lines where the diffusion of knowledge and culture and the extension of services are conceived as a part of the strategic plan of the university as they foster creativity, innovation, interaction with other environments which allows the creation of new and effective responses that serve preventing obsolescence in the academic world.

5.4. University management and social responsibility

The last area where universities interact internal and externally with society is through their administration; although management has always been *part* of the university as it has -one way or another- been administered, only in recent decades has management become a topic of systematic analysis. Central for our study is the way in which higher education institutions are managed as this too has much to say regarding to how responsible universities are.

In the previous sections we have seen that different definitions and approaches to social responsibility of the university share the underlying assumption that these institutions have a key social function in terms of imparting and putting into practice a set of principles and values, through the interaction of three major roles: teaching, research and outreach.

These roles constitute the *traditional* channels through which universities have interacted with society and responded to their needs and demands. However, what happens with the social responsibility of the university when looking inwards? What role does the management of the university have in terms of making higher education institutions act responsibly?

Vallaey (2009) addresses these questions by adding to the traditional trinity (teach, research and outreach) the concept of *management of the university* as one more aspect that, even if it has always been an important element of the life of these institutions, it has remained mostly unseen and neglected from the point of view of the social responsibility.

This author makes an important contribution in the understanding of what social responsibility of the university means as, according to his theoretical framework, being socially responsible represents an adjustment of the behavior of an organization to ethical norms of management toward sustainable development of the person and society.

Hence Managing a university in a responsible way includes aspects that can be observed *indoors* (these refer for instance to the way personnel in the university are treated by the institution and the people with higher hierarchies, how personnel is selected and under what conditions) and *outdoors* (as responsible management also includes the relation of the university to its external and internal providers and other stakeholders it interacts with; also in the design of its campus in terms of materials utilized, practicality and accessibility, and the environmental impacts of its activities both within and outside the campus).

As such, being responsible also represents a form of organizational management, based on how universities are administered in regards to issues like labor conditions, academic efficiency, and the environmental impacts it produces in relation to society as a whole.

According to this approach, social responsibility of the university refers to the *management of the impacts* (direct or collateral) and effects it produces in the community where it works as a consequence of its decisions and activities within and outside its walls.

Therefore, acting responsibly for a university in this sense means making proper diagnosis, taking necessary measures to prevent negative possible impacts and maximizing positive ones that the university can generate for both its internal community and society in general.

Olvera & Gasca (2012) cite a later publication of Vallaeys from 2010, where he goes on to assert that the notion of management of impacts is what makes an organization move from a limited personal kind of ethic behavior toward a systematic and institutional sense of need to respond and contribute to the common good.

When universities are aware of this and decide to use it as a strategy to act responsibly, they overcome their traditional academic autism and open their eyes and arms towards society, by internalizing its externalities, by recognizing problems and participating in the solutions with specific contributions, with management decisions based on accountable interaction.

From the perspective of these authors social responsibility of the university is understood as a *procedural strategy* aimed at giving direction to actions and processes taken by different actors in the context of the university and as such it can be seen as standing on three pillars:

1. An intelligent management of the university;
2. The participation of interest groups; and
3. The management of impacts within and outside the institution.

The activities carried out in and by the universities have different sorts of impacts that affect society in many ways and areas, in general lines Vallaeys classifies them as:

1. Organizational impacts that constitute the aspects of *life in campus*, including labor and environment aspects that affect the lives of people working in the university and their families on everyday bases.
2. Educational impacts that relate to the processes of teaching and learning and the construction of curricula that gives graduates a desired formation and profile.
3. Cognitive impacts refer to the epistemological and deontological orientation universities choose for their programs, and to the approach they give to the research they do. This refers to the kind and purpose of knowledge they produce and who they mean to serve.
4. Social impacts refer to the linkages the university creates and holds with external actors, their contribution and involvement in the creation of social capital. This relates to the role the universities assume before society, commitments with whom and for what purpose typically in outreach activities.

From that classification of areas of impact one can expect that when universities are aware of the kinds of impacts they produce they are able to manage their activities and programs to minimize negative effects and maximize positive ones. To do it, they need to consider policies and strategies within their own institutional frameworks, the vision they have of themselves, the programs they offer, and the way they envision themselves within the broader societal context, which again, leads to the central role of the managers of the institutions.

According to Vallaeys (2009) when universities aim at acting responsibly they do it through the policies they implement at all levels and they are the result from a critical view of their own missions and goals. At the management level, for a university to be considered socially responsible it needs to show concrete accomplishments observed through indicators like:

1. An exemplary institutional life; meaning that its policies are transparent and include labor and environmental standards that promote positive decisions to achieve a *responsible campus* that is coherent with the goals and the mission of the university.
2. Promoting responsible attitudes among citizens by providing an integral formation to the students as constructive participants in the life of their societies. Which means

using teaching methods that promote creative thinking and engagement of the academic community in the solution of social problems.

3. Ensuring a social management of knowledge to overcome irresponsible science by promoting research that is transparent, participatory and democratic. And
4. Promoting social participation that is caring and engages academic and non-academic communities toward the solution of problems in their agendas to allow for mutual learning and development, and for the creation of new networks and social capital.

The framework above explains why for this author social responsibility of the university overflows the concepts of university outreach or extension, because these indicators evidence an institutional commitment at all levels that includes all academic, non-academic and administrative personnel and processes of the university in addressing social matters.

In the view of the author the above does not mean that universities should not carry on with their initiatives of outreach and extension, but instead that they should find ways to *systematize* that interaction with society through structured policies that put those initiatives in line with the rest of the university including management, teaching and researching as interconnected segments and as processes rather than functions.

Hence Vallaeys (2009) concludes that strategies toward the implementation of socially responsible universities need to promote:

1. Participation and integration of groups of interest within and outside the university;
2. Articulation of study plans, research, extension and teaching methods with the solution to problems beyond the university itself; and
3. A regular diagnosis of the work done with transparency and accountability.

Adding to that idea, Gaete Quezada noticed that among good practices on implementation of responsible behaviors and the achievement of good standards in university management in relation to its interactions, both within and outside campus, a positive strategy is keeping proper records and documentation in the institutional and program frameworks.

According to this author accurate and up-to-date institutional records help universities' managers know where they stand in terms of their goals and how they achieve them. When universities account with properly implemented documentation mechanisms and systems to track evidence, this provides transparency to the process of strategic planning, management and to the actions taken by the universities to accomplish their missions.

Keeping good institutional records relates to being accountable, specially for those in charge of making decisions that affect the whole body; it is a well-know fact that the flip side of governance is accountability; and this is what universities should strive for in the search for a well-grounded and responsibly managed system.

At the university level accountability means that management of administration, educational programs, research and extension and outreach activities are subject to a review and as such they can be evaluated and changed or sustained over time. This means that for universities to accomplish their mission they need to account with the trust from their external partners in the implementation of the socially responsible projects in whatever their form.

The above implies that the management of the university and its connections to the external world are more than just technical aspects of the management of life in campus, this is so because it is in the everyday contact that students are confronted with daily issues that result from living together, which includes not only people, but also structures, political procedures, taking decisions that affect the group as a whole and finding solutions to emerging conflicts.

Another example of the fact that management is more than a technical matter is the fact that university's governance and community governance are relevant in terms of how joint projects evolve over time. The governing structures and people in charge within the structure of universities and the communities greatly affect the continuity of joint projects and the engagement of the partners.

For instance the deans of some faculties may have sufficient authority or influence to decide on the commitment from his or her institution to a social project, and the same can be said from those local authorities that account with the power to make changes in the engagement of the community as a whole. Changes in the structure of power of both sides of the partnership can affect the life and outcomes of community projects and the relations of the university to its surrounding environment.

This new vision of the management of the university as a whole shifts the analysis from the traditional segmented management of the university (in three pillars: teaching, researching and extension and outreach) by focusing in the inclusion of a fourth pillar: management as an integrative approach to social responsibility of the university.

This takes us one step forward in the analysis of what social responsibility of the university is. As we mentioned in the literature review in chapter 2 the international ISO norms in their ISO 26000 on social responsibility provide a systematic approach to the issue, which, although not specifically meant for universities makes an important contribution in the connection between the concepts of management and social responsibility at the institutional level.

These are –as previously explained- a set of internationally recognized guidelines that define social responsibility of the organizations aiming to provide guidance to institutions wishing to act responsibly. Coinciding with Vallaey's work on the universities' role of management in acting responsibly the ISO 26000 guidelines define social responsibility in terms of the liability an organization has for the impacts that its decisions and activities produce both within and outside its walls, as compared to an ethic and transparent behavior that is consistent with social wellbeing and sustainable development of surrounding communities, that is also inclusive of the perspectives and needs of the parties that are affected and that complies with legal requisites at all levels (local, national and international).

According to the principles set there, for any organization wishing to act responsibly, universities too need to relate to their communities through a strategy that is integrated to the whole of it and not only to some *patches* in the structure, that is involving, or at a minimum considering, in the strategy all its activities, its *influence zones* through their four roles: teaching, researching, outreach and management.

A last reflection to be made here is that a well-grounded socially responsible strategy must be applicable to all its inter-institutional relations, within and outside the university, therefore actively promoting the participation of all major related stakeholders.

6. Conclusion: university social responsibility as institutional identity

Through the previous pages this study has described the phenomenon of social responsibility of the university in an integrative manner to include various approaches and areas where any university is expected to act responsibly.

For most organizations acting responsibly relates to authentic will to help and provide new solutions to the everyday problems, however in many cases these activities also respond to rather selfish goals such as gaining social visibility and acceptance from targeted audiences.

In both cases universities are not exception to this; however they stand in a unique point within the constellation of social actors due to their history, the very definition of what universities are, even more intrinsically due to the function they have been assigned and the missions they are expected to accomplish.

Through history universities have interacted differently with society, this is because societies and universities have changed overtime. However as we saw through previous pages, the university has always had an intrinsic role as a social transformer based on its capacity to impart education and values, while being a nest for social and technical innovation, interacting with other social agents (although in different ways) through what it teaches, what it researches, what it offers to society through outreach and extension and in whatever ways it seeks to improve society and to bring new forms of social justice and inclusion.

We recall Fitzgerald (2006) in saying that there are differences between what one can expect from traditional academic activities as compared to those more socially engaged; for example, in more conservative universities, professors and researchers offer instruction to students in classrooms and laboratories, they carry out research that is based on scientific paradigms with goals set by researchers and where outputs of that research is meant to be disseminated through academic journals and books; meaning that at the end of the day members of the academic community work to serve and benefit the academic community itself.

As we have seen through this study, in the case of universities that engage socially they opt for more socially sensitive approaches to their work and their interactions with society; this makes teaching an experience that goes beyond the formal accreditation of the learning process, allowing learning to happen *in* and *outside* campus, as community-based activities that give access to real life exposure where students advance knowledge in professional, technical *and* personal terms.

Responsible research too works differently as it happens through collaborative partnerships, where goals and procedures are set on common agreement and for the mutual benefit of the university and external communities seeking to improve social conditions while remaining scientific and evidence-based practice.

And the same can be said when universities engage in social service as faculty members commit in contributing to the betterment of the community by using the resources they account with, working as professionals, providing guidance and advise, offering research-based policy recommendations to legislators and policy makers or even acting as volunteers.

Clearly, it is through what universities do and through their interactions that they affect and produce impacts in their communities both within and outside their campuses and their academic fields; therefore it is in the way universities envision and manage those effects that one can see a university acting responsibly.

Acting responsible for a university means achieving the mission it has set for itself while minimizing negative impacts and maximizing the creation of solutions and positive social influences through all its activities: teaching, research, outreach, extension and management.

Because of their roles and due to the kind of institutions they are universities can never believe that they are once and for all socially responsible, based on the assumption that by seeking to accomplish their missions of looking at social problems through their traditional roles (teaching, researching and doing extension and outreach) they automatically contribute to the improvement and development of their societies. The previous pages demonstrate that acting responsible is a matter of daily decisions with constant evaluation and change.

In this sense we agree with Vallaey (2009) when he argues that in no case an institution is *a priori* and by definition immune to acting irresponsibly. All institutions may at a certain point produce negative impacts, even if initially well intentioned. When it comes to acting responsibly no individual and no institution has *a responsible seal* attached before hand and for good. The level to which that responsibility is accomplished greatly depends on its capacity to have a critical inner look; to make proper diagnosis of the impacts it produces (or does not produce even if it could potentially do it); to stay open to dialogue and include all interested parties (with transparency and accountability) in the decisions it makes; and to comply with legal standards at all levels in all its initiatives and actions.

The idea of social responsibility of the university as a management strategy implies this is not an outcome but a never-ending process; meaning that universities go through a course of *social responsabilization*, because no organization can ever completely finish the work of managing all its impacts and possible ways of contributing to the improvement of social problems. At the same time it can never include all interested parties in the dialogue and construction of strategies in the problems it decides to address. Based on this, Vallaey (2009) concludes saying that social improvement and organizational development is a never-ending process, not a status or a qualitative adjective that any university can obtain once and for all.

Specifically for universities, acting socially responsible is a way through which they can better integrate the traditionally fragmented parts and functions of the institution. This means that a responsible university will normally coordinate the four processes: management, academic formation, research, and outreach and extension with the demands coming from society in terms of scientific development, professional and educational development, local and global development that in all cases is democratic, fair and sustainable.

Therefore social responsibility of the university is more than an instrument or a strategy of the institution to connect to the community, it is a feature that defines the nature and the quality in the kind of organization it is and it wants to be.

If a university sees itself as a channel for change, as a mechanism that can transform the social tissue and contribute toward the sustainable development of the community and the country, then this is one of the ways through which it can materialize its potentials.

Hernandez & Saldarriga (2009) express a similar idea in saying that social responsibility of the university is, more than anything, one way of behaving ethically, it means assuming an active role, a position regarding the positive and negative aspects of the decisions related to the common good.

However understanding the social role of the university in those terms puts us in front of a paradigmatic dilemma regarding the roles the university should have all together; Sandmann (n.d.) answers to that quest by recalling scholar Phil Nyden from Loyola University in saying that "*engaged scholarship is messy work and messy research, but... neat results*" and that in order to obtain those neat results, universities need to anchor their commitments through the policies, documents, networks and plans of each institution.

The above leads us to conclude that the role of the university is actually much more than being a mere knowledge producer and impartor. As we have seen through these pages the

developments through which higher education has gone in recent decades in the field of pedagogy focus on new teaching/learning experiences and the application of methodologies like service learning and the use of competency based curriculum that aim at creating opportunities for students to design, implement and evaluate activities that go beyond the typical learning processes taking place in the classrooms.

These kinds of learning experiences materialize through giving social services; while in so doing they blend together apprenticeship, reinforce ethical values and produce a feeling of citizenship driven engagement.

The same can be said about engaging research with the needs and views of the communities in ways that are scientifically proven yet connected to the practical solution of everyday problems. In engaging the communities in participatory ways in their research universities become open channels for synergy, which clearly are not exempt from conflict, yet with great potentials for social change and advancement.

As modern societies become more complex and fluid, they also become more anonymous creating fertile soils for seeds that create social systems that even if they can be classified as democracies they lack the sense of care and support from effective citizens and it is exactly there that universities have their biggest potential to accomplish their missions.

In the view of Olvera & Gasca (2012) it is in this point, globalized and anonymous societies where universities can offer not only a remedy to many of the world's social problems but more importantly they carry in themselves the seeds to create more open spaces and foster participation among citizens toward the consolidation of democratic principles in all societies.

It is clear that the 21st century brings challenges to universities and that they will need to evaluate their roles with their eyes into the future. Universities will not be immune to the changes that societies are going through and as such they will need to develop new strategies for interaction and to continue to contribute to the advancement of human kind.

This scenario confronts universities with the need to address tensions between the traditional roles it was assigned and what they are expected to do now in terms of producing effective human resources that are sensitive individuals and capable of independent and critical thinking, while interacting with other social entities in the context of the global markets.

In today's world the role of the university relates to the need of providing human resources capable of inserting themselves in more competitive models of production of goods and services; yet training responsible and creative workforces, reinforcing productive research, and from there contributing to the economic and social development of their nations.

Olvera & Gasca recall that in the view of Mollis (2010) it is this new context what ensures a preeminent role for the university as responsible organizations work toward the formation of responsible citizens; even if markets and new technologies are challenging the perceptions regarding the role of the university by pushing and demanding from them the formation of competent workers, truth is they are expected to actually give something else, something *humane*.

According to Vallaeys (2009) universities wishing to move from typical institutional view of themselves towards an integral social responsibility approach need to design and implement a plan that includes developing a strategy for communication to allow all stakeholders not only to *know* about the university's goals but also to *understand* them, *contribute* to them and to *own* them. Once this is achieved three more important actions are necessary to be implemented and maintained over time:

1. Self-diagnosis. The university must ask itself *by doing what we are doing; what are we really doing?* In other words, by teaching this or that, by researching on this, or participating in that activity, by making this diagnosis... what abilities are we developing in our students and in the academic community as a whole? How do our activities change or improve the performance of the university and the impacts it produces in all areas?
2. Be accountable. The university needs to clearly show what it does, this implies institutional transparency, both internal and externally and refers to setting clear goals and procedures that can be tracked over time to evaluate actions, continue in the same directions or change them if necessary.
3. Be trustworthy. When a university does what it says it does, when it is congruent with the declarations it does, it gains authority and credibility and in so doing it can better accomplish its mission and vision.

So we can see that acting as a socially responsible institution defines who a university is. This represents to it much more than a brand or a social mark for recognition, it is a sign of who it is, and who it wants to be.

It is the university's responsibility to promote changes that bring about social justice, inclusion and advancement; it is in its own heart to transform social structures toward societies that are technically and scientifically more advanced but also fairer and more sensitive through the roles and functions that define who they are, hence teaching, researching, carrying out extension and outreach and managing itself.

Social responsibility of the university is not the same as management, or extension and outreach, or teaching or researching, it is all of them together approached in an integral way and applied to practical interactions with the rest of society. It is crucial to make a clear distinction here, and the same goes for the usual confusion that exists in terms of social responsibility of the university and the so-called third role of the university.

As we have seen through these pages, these concepts are related but refer to and define different things, where social responsibility of the university is a much wider concept that includes the university as a whole, as a complete universe that needs to act responsibly in all its areas. Whereas extension and outreach for example refer *only* to one part, one area where universities may decide to act and implement specific project, or not.

Being a socially responsible agent for a university implies being aware and -in as much as possible- in control of the effects of its actions on others, as such teaching, researching, extending its activities and managing itself as a whole call for responsibility.

The university may take measures to address some social problems affecting a communities in its surroundings, however, *being responsible* implies a much bigger engagement, and a much greater institutional effort, because this refers to who the university wants to be, and that includes all areas and forms of interaction the it has with its surroundings.

Universities' responsibilities go beyond producing effective and responsible human resources, doing useful and liable research and reaching out by providing services to a given community and contributing to the economic, social and cultural development of their countries. All of these are doubtlessly key elements to define the role of the university and its responsibilities; however more than the actions themselves it is the goals and motivations driving those actions what makes us understand that the social responsibility of the university is more than anything an engine for social change.

7. References

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